

The Influencing Factors on Consumer Intention to buy Furniture from Online Platform in Egypt - A Case Study of Homzmart.Com

By: Abdelrahman Hany Abbass Elsherbiny

DBA Candidate – The International Business School of Scandinavia

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1. Abstract:

This doctoral thesis examines the key factors influencing consumer intention to purchase furniture from online platforms in Egypt, with a focus on the Homzmart.com platform. The study provides a comprehensive analysis of the Egyptian furniture industry, the growth of e-commerce, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on online shopping trends.

The literature review covers a wide range of factors that can influence online purchase intention, including e-service quality dimensions (e.g., product information, customer service, website design), visual merchandising (brand, color, product positioning), trust and security perceptions, and supply chain performance. The research methodology involved a quantitative survey of Egyptian consumers, with data analysis techniques such as descriptive statistics, factor analysis, regression modeling, and structural equation modeling.

Importance of Research

This study addresses a significant gap in e-commerce research within the Egyptian furniture industry. It is important for several reasons:

- It provides insights into consumer behavior in an emerging e-commerce market for high-involvement products like furniture.
- The findings can guide online furniture retailers in improving their services and increasing consumer trust.
- It contributes to the broader understanding of e-commerce adoption in emerging markets.

The key findings of the study include:

- The importance of trust-building measures, including secure payment options and transparent return policies, to address consumer concerns around financial and delivery risks
- The significance of advanced product visualization tools, such as 3D viewers and augmented reality, to enhance the online furniture shopping experience
- The continued preference for cash on delivery as a payment method, highlighting the need for hybrid payment structures that cater to local consumer preferences
- The influence of brand reputation and social proof on purchase intentions, underscoring the importance of localized marketing strategies

Key Recommendations

- Implement hybrid payment systems and gradually promote digital payment adoption.
- Invest in advanced product visualization technologies.
- Develop strong brand communities and leverage social proof.
- Optimize delivery processes and provide clear customer support policies.
- Ensure mobile optimization of e-commerce platforms.
- Enhance website security features to build consumer trust.

The thesis provides actionable recommendations for online furniture retailers and manufacturers in Egypt, focusing on areas such as trust and security protocols, product information and visualization, delivery optimization, and website design and usability. The findings contribute to the scholarly understanding of e-commerce adoption in emerging markets and offer practical insights for the digital transformation of the Egyptian furniture industry.

2. Introduction

Technology plays a substantial role in changing people's lives and how they are doing business. Linking both people as consumers and companies by technology is a great advantage since it makes selling and buying much more comfortable and efficient with no limitation to time, place, travel cost, and limited product/service variety & options. In general, online shopping & e-commerce is booming, especially with the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic (Statista, 2020), while the furniture industry is very fragmented, and the customer is limited. In this section, the researcher aims to illustrate the furniture industry and how e-commerce could be an opportunity to expand the customer base and resolve the issue of a fragmented market. In addition to the illustration of the Egyptian government's vision about the furniture industry and the information and communication technology (ICT). Finally, the researcher stated this research's objectives and the added value to the writer.

This section flows as below:

- 2.1. [Research Problem](#)
- 2.2. [The Egyptian Furniture Industry](#)
- 2.3. [Online Shopping And E-Commerce – Facts And Figures](#)
- 2.4. [The National E-Commerce Strategy](#)
- 2.5. [COVID-19 Pandemic And The Opportunities For E-Commerce](#)
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- 2.8. [Case Study: Homzmart.com](#)

2.1. Research Problem

Notwithstanding the expansion of e-commerce, the furniture sector in Egypt has been sluggish in embracing online retail. This hesitance arises from multiple aspects, including the tactile aspect of furniture shopping, wherein buyers like physically inspecting things.

- Concerns over product quality, design, and material when making internet purchases.
- Concerns around trust in financial transactions and delivery obligations.
- Inadequate digital literacy among certain furniture sellers and producers.

The disparity between the expanding e-commerce trend and the conventional furniture sector presents a substantial study issue: How can the Egyptian furniture business successfully adapt to e-commerce while confronting the distinct obstacles of online furniture sales?

2.2. The Egyptian Furniture Industry

The historical context of Egypt's furniture industry merits scholarly examination, as it encompasses a rich heritage extending to antiquity. Egypt's contributions to furniture craftsmanship have been notable throughout history, characterized by sophisticated design elements and exemplary artisanal techniques (Killen, 2011). While the industry's roots are deeply embedded in ancient traditions, it has undergone substantial transformations over the course of the 20th and 21st centuries.

The ancient Egyptian furniture industry was distinguished by its elaborate designs and superior craftsmanship, often incorporating symbolic motifs and utilizing precious materials. These artifacts not only served functional purposes but also reflected the social, religious, and aesthetic values of their time. Archaeological evidence and historical records provide valuable insights into the techniques, materials, and cultural significance of furniture in ancient Egyptian society (Harcombe, 2011).

In contrast, the contemporary furniture industry in Egypt has experienced significant evolution, particularly over the last hundred years. This transformation has been influenced by various factors, including technological advancements, changing consumer preferences, global trade dynamics, and socioeconomic developments within the country (Council, 2011). The juxtaposition of traditional craftsmanship with modern manufacturing processes presents an intriguing area for academic inquiry, offering opportunities to explore the industry's adaptation to changing market demands while preserving cultural heritage.

The modern Egyptian furniture industry faces challenges and opportunities in the global market. El Zeiny (2020) highlights the potential for cultural-oriented design as a strategy for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to gain a competitive advantage. By incorporating elements of traditional Egyptian culture into modern furniture design, companies can create unique value propositions that appeal to both domestic and international consumers.

Further research into this topic could elucidate the specific trajectories of change, the impact of industrialization on traditional techniques, and the industry's current position in both domestic and international markets. Such an investigation would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of Egypt's furniture industry, bridging its ancient legacy with its modern manifestations.

The evolution of Egypt's furniture industry over the past seven decades has been marked by significant milestones and market transformations. This progression can be delineated into several key phases:

- 1950s-1960s: This period witnessed the establishment of state-owned furniture factories, primarily focused on mass production to meet domestic demand (El-Meehy, 2002). This initiative was part of the broader industrialization efforts undertaken by the Egyptian government during this era.
- 1970s-1980s: The furniture industry experienced a notable shift with the emergence of private sector manufacturers. This development led to a diversification in both styles and

quality of furniture products, reflecting the changing economic policies and consumer preferences of the time (Handoussa, 1994).

- 1990s: A significant turning point occurred as the industry began to prioritize exports, particularly to Arab countries. The export value exhibited remarkable growth, increasing from \$5 million in 1990 to \$40 million by 1999 (El-Haddad, 2012). This expansion can be attributed to economic liberalization policies and improved regional trade relations.
- 2000s: The new millennium brought challenges in the form of intensified competition from imported furniture, particularly from China. Import figures rose dramatically, with a 200% increase observed between 2000 and 2006 (Zohry, 2007). This surge in imports had profound implications for local manufacturers and market dynamics.
- 2010s: The most recent decade has been characterized by a resurgence of local manufacturers. This revival has been distinguished by a strategic focus on blending traditional Egyptian craftsmanship with modern design aesthetics, aiming to create a unique value proposition in both domestic and international markets (El Zeiny, 2020).

2.2.1. The furniture industry in numbers

Tarek A. and Khaled W. (2002) stated that Damietta city is the premier location for furniture in Egypt. It accounts for approximately 60% of Egypt's Gross National Product (GNP) in furniture and 25% of the overall establishments within the country's furniture industry (Al Etr & Wahba, 2002). It ranks as the third largest industry in terms of staff count and the number of factories and workshops (EFEC, 2016).

In 2016, the Egyptian Furniture Export Council released a report concerning the furniture sector. The furniture industry experienced significant growth from 2010 to 2014, with a market size rise of 56% and a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 4.1% (refer to Figure 1). Production rose by 67%, while exports surged by 79%. Small and medium-sized enterprises account for 70% of the total furniture establishments in Egypt (EFEC, 2016).

Figure 1: A graph showing the furniture market size in Egypt over the years starting from 2010 till 2015, then forecast from 2017 till 2020

Source: (EFEC, 2016)

2.2.2. Furniture industry SWOT analysis

The Egyptian furniture industry plays a significant role in the country's economy, contributing to both domestic consumption and export revenue. To comprehensively understand the industry's current position and future prospects, a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis is essential. This analysis draws upon the seminal work of Tarek A. and Khaled W. (2002) and incorporates more recent data from the Egyptian Furniture Export Council report (2016) [1]. The following sections provide an in-depth examination of the industry's internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats.

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

1. Rich Cultural Heritage and Craftsmanship
 - Egypt's furniture industry benefits from a long-standing tradition of craftsmanship, dating back to ancient times (*Tarek, 2002*).
 - The industry leverages unique designs incorporating traditional Egyptian motifs, providing a competitive advantage in both domestic and international markets (*EFEC, 2016*).
2. Competitive Labor Costs
 - Relatively low labor costs compared to many competing countries contribute to cost-effective production (*Tarek, 2002*).
 - A skilled workforce, particularly in traditional woodworking techniques, enhances product quality and uniqueness (*EFEC, 2016*).
3. Strategic Geographic Location
 - Egypt's position facilitates easy access to European, Middle Eastern, and African markets, reducing transportation costs and time (*Tarek, 2002*).
4. Government Support
 - Implementation of supportive policies and initiatives, such as the National E-commerce Strategy, aims to boost online sales and modernize the industry (*Industry, 2018*).
5. Growing Domestic Market
 - A large and young population drives demand for furniture products (*EFEC, 2016*).
 - Increasing urbanization and housing projects contribute to sustained market growth (*Statistics, 2022*).

Weaknesses

1. Limited Technological Integration
 - Slow adoption of modern production technologies, particularly among small and medium-sized manufacturers (*Tarek, 2002*).
 - Limited implementation of e-commerce platforms and digital marketing strategies (*EFEC, 2016*).
2. Quality Control Issues
 - Inconsistent quality standards across the industry, particularly in smaller workshops (*Tarek, 2002*).
 - Lack of widespread adoption of international quality certifications, potentially hindering export opportunities (*EFEC, 2016*).

3. Raw Material Dependency
 - High reliance on imported raw materials, affecting production costs and sustainability efforts (*Tarek, 2002*).
 - Vulnerability to international price fluctuations and supply chain disruptions (*EFEC, 2016*).
4. Limited Research and Development
 - Insufficient investment in R&D activities to drive innovation and product development (*Tarek, 2002*).
 - Lack of strong industry-academia partnerships to foster innovation (*EFEC, 2016*).
5. Informal Sector Dominance
 - A significant portion of the industry operates in the informal sector, leading to challenges in standardization and quality control (*Tarek, 2002*).

Opportunities

1. Export Market Expansion
 - Growing demand for Egyptian furniture in Middle Eastern and African markets (*EFEC, 2016*).
 - Potential for entering new markets with unique, culturally inspired designs (*Tarek, 2002*).
2. E-commerce Growth
 - Increasing consumer comfort with online furniture shopping, particularly post-pandemic (*EFEC, 2016*).
 - Potential for reaching a wider customer base through digital platforms (*Industry, 2018*).
3. Sustainable Furniture Trend
 - Growing global demand for eco-friendly and sustainable furniture options (*EFEC, 2016*).
 - Opportunity to develop recycled and upcycled furniture lines, leveraging Egypt's traditional craftsmanship (*Tarek, 2002*).
4. Technological Integration
 - Potential for AR/VR adoption to enhance online shopping experiences and reduce return rates (*EFEC, 2016*).
 - Integration of smart furniture and IoT technologies to meet evolving consumer needs (*MCIT, 2021*).
5. Customization and Personalization
 - Increasing demand for customized furniture solutions in both domestic and international markets (*EFEC, 2016*).
 - Opportunity to leverage traditional craftsmanship for high-value, bespoke pieces (*Tarek, 2002*).

Threats

1. International Competition
 - Increasing competition from low-cost manufacturers in Asia, particularly China (*Tarek, 2002*).

- Presence of established global brands in the domestic market, potentially eroding market share (EFEC, 2016).
2. Economic Instability
 - Fluctuations in currency exchange rates affecting import costs and export competitiveness (Tarek, 2002).
 - Potential economic downturns impacting consumer spending on furniture (EFEC, 2016).
 3. Raw Material Price Volatility
 - Fluctuating prices of wood and other raw materials impacting production costs (Tarek, 2002).
 - Potential supply chain disruptions affecting production schedules and delivery times (EFEC, 2016).
 4. Changing Consumer Preferences
 - Rapid shifts in design trends requiring quick adaptations and flexible production capabilities (EFEC, 2016).
 - Growing preference for multifunctional and space-saving furniture in urban areas, challenging traditional design approaches (Tarek, 2002).
 5. Regulatory Challenges
 - Potential changes in export regulations or trade agreements affecting international market access (EFEC, 2016).
 - Stricter environmental regulations potentially impact production processes and costs (Environment, 2020).

This SWOT analysis provides a comprehensive overview of the Egyptian furniture industry’s current position and future prospects. It highlights the need for technological integration, quality improvement, and sustainable practices while leveraging the country’s rich cultural heritage and growing market opportunities. The industry’s ability to address its weaknesses and capitalize on emerging opportunities will be crucial for its long-term success and competitiveness in both domestic and international markets.

Table 1: SWOT analysis for the furniture industry in Egypt

Domain	Description	References
Strengths	A large number of specialized establishments with skilled workers	(Tarek, 2002). (EFEC, 2016)
	Low-cost labor compared to international markets (See Figure 2)	(Tarek, 2002). (EFEC, 2016)
	The industry is fixable	(EFEC, 2016)
	International trade agreements	(EFEC, 2016)
Weakness	Very fragmented industry	(Tarek, 2002). (EFEC, 2016)
	Resistance to change	(Tarek, 2002).
	Lacks a marketing strategy	(Tarek, 2002). (EFEC, 2016)
	Lacks standard operating procedures & quality	(Tarek, 2002). (EFEC, 2016)
	The productivity of labor and manufactures are very low compared to other developing countries	(Tarek, 2002). (EFEC, 2016)

General access

Opportunities	The real estate industry for residence and offices is booming	(EFEC, 2016)
	Government support in terms of mega projects (The New Dumyat Furniture City), subsidies, and consulting	(EFEC, 2016)
Risks	The imports from China are putting pressure on local manufacturers to compete (See Figure 3)	(Tarek, 2002). (EFEC, 2016)
	Some Importers are declaring fake invoices for the imported goods to pay fewer customs fees, which reflected in the product selling price	(EFEC, 2016)
	The government subsidy program is weak	(EFEC, 2016)

Source: (Al Etr & Wahba, 2002) (EFEC, 2016)

Figure 2: A graph of annual employee wages (2010/2011) comparing between Egypt and other countries

Source: (EFEC, 2016)

Source: (EFEC, 2016)

In Figure 3, the total production of furniture in Egypt is less than the imports, which indicates the opportunity for local players to compete by fulfilling this gap between production and imports (EFEC, 2016).

Figure 3: A graph showing the total value of furniture production, import & export in the Egyptian market year over a year starting from 2010 till 2015

Source: (EFEC, 2016)

2.2.3. The difference between business models in the furniture industry

Subject matter specialists in the furniture industry indicate that the majority of the sector in Egypt continues to function through conventional methods, including "offline trading." This conventional approach to commerce within this sector encompasses various models:

1. A workshop manufactures bespoke products for B2B and B2C (Make-to-order). It mostly relies on reputation, trustworthiness, and goodwill. Typically, these workshops are small to medium scale. They lack a showroom. They manufacture on demand, hence, without inventory.
2. Workshops manufacture their designs as stock (make-to-stock) offered across their showrooms; also, they can develop bespoke products for both B2B and B2C. This model relies on reputation, trustworthiness, and benevolence. Also, the exposure caused by having showrooms helps to get traffic, resulting to greater sales than the previous model (with dependent on the showroom's location and the traffic)—the size of these organizations is usually medium size.
3. This business model resembles the second model; however, production may be outsourced due to constrained capacity amid rising demand.
4. The last model is just a showroom, in which they purchase finished products and stock from local producers or foreign furniture products.

2.2.4. Government support for the furniture industry

The furniture sector ranks as the third-largest industry in Egypt, measured by employee count and the quantity of factories and workshops (EFEC, 2016). This exceptional standing in the industry necessitates governmental assistance to meet local demand by enhancing domestic output and diminishing imports, so alleviating pressure on the national trade deficit and augmenting exports to regional and global markets. Three pillars of government support that are capitalizing on the industry strengths to capture the possibilities and develop its shortcomings to tackle the dangers (EFEC, 2016):

- Technical & business consulting

The Egyptian Furniture Export Council's 2016 report indicates that the Ministry of Trade and Industry tasked them, together with the Industrial Modernization Center of Egypt (IMC), to deliver consultation services encompassing both technical and business dimensions. This mandate seeks to elevate the furniture business, enhancing its competitiveness both locally and, crucially, at regional and worldwide levels.

- Fiscal assistance

The financial assistance is being allocated through export subsidies to enhance Egypt's exports across all sectors. The Ministry of Trade and Industry funds this export subsidy initiative. (EFEC, 2016)

- Furniture industry sector and infrastructure

In December 2019, the New Dumyat Furniture City was opened by the Egyptian president Abdelfatah Elsisy, as it is regarded as one of the most significant national projects in Egypt. This major project intends to make it the destination for the domestic market and the regional &

international markets due to its tradition in this industry, its geographical location, and the well-developed infrastructure in this new industrial zone (ESIS, 2019).

2.3. Online Shopping and E-Commerce – Facts and Figures

Online shopping has become a realistic preference for many consumers worldwide as the Internet has become a critical communication tool for companies (Ariffin, et al., 2018). According to Internet World Stats (2020), 63.2% of the global population are Internet users, reflecting a rise of 1,266% from the year 2000. Africa accounts for around 13% of the global internet user base, reflecting a growth of 13,898% since the year 2000. In Egypt, 48.1% of its population, are internet users, with an increase of 10,840% from the year 2000 (Statista, 2020). Globally, the average monthly visits to internet retailers' websites totaled 21.9 billion (Statista, 2020). In 2019, worldwide internet sales amounted to USD 3.53 trillion, constituting 14.1% of total retail sales, with projections indicating an increase to 22% by 2023 (Statista, 2020).

2.4. The National E-Commerce Strategy

By considering the numbers of online shopping and the considerable potential of e-commerce in Egypt, and with the rapid technological development and innovation, the furniture industry should capitalize on this as an opportunity. The UNCTAD (2017) report mentioned that Egypt (at the time of writing this proposal) has the largest population of online shoppers in the Arab world as the Egyptian consumer market is more than 90 million inhabitants, around 60% of them are younger than 30 years old (54 million), and 30 million Internet users in 2015/2016 with an internet penetration of 37.8%. Also, they mentioned, in addition to the potential on the local level, Egypt's geographical location makes regional potential untapped yet. The ICT sector in Egypt is one of the fastest-growing sectors, with almost 3% of the 2015/2016 GDP (UNCTAD, 2017). The Business to Consumer (B2C) is estimated to have reached USD544 million in 2015/2016, representing 0.4% of total retail (UNCTAD, 2017).

The national e-commerce strategy of Egypt has three angles (UNCTAD, 2017)¹:

- Capitalizing on Egypt's key strengths in ICT
 - a. Mobile penetration about 110% (Urban and rural areas)
 - b. 37.8% of Egyptians are using the Internet (Urban and rural areas) at the time of the published report in 2017, and in 2020 it has increased to 48.1% (Statista, 2020)
 - c. Rolling out the 4th generation telecom technology that will improve broadband services
 - d. Currently, the ministry of telecommunication is working to replace the copper infrastructure with fiber optics across the country
 - e. Data centers infrastructure for could computing industry
- Tackling the key challenges
 - f. Continue developing the ICT infrastructure and telecom services

¹ This strategy has been developed in 2017

- g. Developing the logistics facilities that ensure a fast, reliable & trackable delivery system.
 - h. E-commerce regulation needs to strengthen more
 - i. Developing more the solution for electronic payments
 - j. Developing specific taxation policy for E-commerce
 - k. Diversified e-commerce platforms
 - l. Skills development towards digital technology
 - m. Educating the Egyptian consumer about e-commerce by raising awareness towards its benefits
 - n. For the business to business, raising the awareness of the benefits of electronic procurement and tendering
- Capturing the opportunities
 - o. A population of 60% of youth (less than 30 years old), as well as the skilled labor, especially in the sector of Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) and Information Technology Enabled Services (ITES)
 - p. A sound regulatory framework for electronic payments
 - q. A large consumer base that is not tapped yet

2.5. COVID-19 Pandemic and The Opportunities For E-Commerce

“When written in Chinese, the word ‘crisis’ is composed of two characters, one represents danger, and the other represents opportunity.” John f. Kennedy

COVID-19 pandemic has impacted nearly the whole world with economic and social implications. More than 78 million confirmed cases of COVID-19 and 1.7 million deaths worldwide (Worldometers, 2020). This pandemic forced many countries to lockdown and created measures to restrict citizens’ mobility and business operations to contain the spread of COVID-19. As many people stayed home in early 2020 to contain the spread of the COVID-19, digital channels have become the first alternative to offline stores to avoid crowds. In June 2020, 22 billion monthly online shopping visits were recorded worldwide, and the demand was remarkably high for everyday items such as groceries, clothing, and retail electronics items. (Statista, 2020)

Mr. Amr Mahfouze, the CEO of the Information Technology Industry Development of Egypt (ITID), said that the COVID-19 pandemic had created exceptional circumstances that imposed new life patterns on the whole world. This new pattern contributed to a suitable environment for adopting digital services, transactions, and more reliance on new digital models of doing business and learning remotely (MoCIT, 2020).

According to the American Chamber of Commerce report in Egypt (2020), the UNCTAD downgraded its global GDP forecasts below 2.5%. Regarding Egypt, GDP projected (pre-crisis of COVID-19) to grow by 2% in 2020 and 2.8% in 2021. However, the Ministry of Planning and Economic Development stated that GDP is 4.5% in Q3 2019/20, and expected to become 3.5% in Q4 and recover in 2021 to be 4.7%, according to ECES report (2020).

One of the opportunities mentioned in Fitch's (2020) report for the retail industry in Egypt is that the COVID-19 crisis caused an increase in the number of consumers who embraced e-commerce, creating medium-term opportunities for the online retailers. (Solutions, 2020) The impact on the ICT sector in Egypt, the National Telecom Regulatory Authority (2020) report mentioned that the ICT activities had been increased significantly from the period of the 2nd week of March to the 2nd week of April, and the 3rd week of April to the 3rd week of May (NTRA, 2020).

- **Web browsing** increased 131% in the 2nd week of April 2020 compared to the 2nd week of March 2020 (NTRA, 2020)
- **Mobile internet usage** increased by 35%, as well as **home internet** also increased by 99%² (NTRA, 2020)
- During Summer 2020, **online shopping** recorded in one hour 0.2 million customers and 1.5 million visits, while **web browsing** recorded 1 million users and 86 million visits (NTRA, 2020)
- Comparing summer 2020 with summer 2019, the usage of **ADSL internet** increased by 92%, and **mobile internet usage** increased by 12% (NTRA, 2020)
- There is a 14.4 million **E-wallet for mobile phones** as of October 2020, with 9.9 million transactions. Comparing October 2020 figures with March 2020, there is a 17% increase in the number of E-wallets and a 156% increase in the number of transactions (NTRA, 2020)
- 48% of **E-Wallets owners** are less than 36 years old, and 89% are less than 56 years old (NTRA, 2020)

2.6. Research Objectives and Questions

This study aims to investigate the factors influencing Egyptian consumers' intention to purchase furniture from online platforms, using Homzmart.com as a case study. The research objectives are:

1. To identify and analyze the e-service quality factors that influence online furniture purchase intentions in Egypt.
2. To examine the relationship between these factors and overall service quality and customer satisfaction.
3. To assess Homzmart's e-service quality performance in the context of these factors.

The main research question guiding this study is:

² Compared to the internet usage for both before COVID-19 pandemic

1. What are the key e-service quality factors influencing Egyptian consumers' intention to purchase furniture from online platforms?
2. Secondary research questions include:
3. How do these factors contribute to overall service quality and customer satisfaction?
4. How does Homzmart.com perform in terms of these e-service quality factors?
5. What strategies can online furniture retailers in Egypt adopt to enhance consumer trust and purchase intention?

2.7. Significance of the Study

This research is significant for several reasons:

- Addressing a Gap in the Literature:

The theses highlight the limited academic attention paid to e-commerce in the Egyptian furniture industry. By focusing specifically on this domain, the current study helps fill an important gap in the existing knowledge base.

- Providing Practical Insights for Furniture Retailers and Manufacturers:

The in-depth analysis of consumer behavior and purchase intentions in the online furniture retail context, as presented in the theses, offers valuable practical insights that can directly benefit furniture e-tailers and manufacturers in Egypt. These insights can help them better understand and address the unique concerns and preferences of their target customers.

- Contributing to the Understanding of E-commerce Adoption in Developing Economies:

The theses highlight the importance of examining e-commerce trends and challenges within the context of emerging markets, such as Egypt. By focusing on the furniture industry, this research contributes to the broader understanding of digital transformation in traditional industries in developing economies.

- Informing Policy Decisions:

The findings from this study can help inform policy decisions related to supporting the digital transformation of the furniture industry and shaping appropriate e-commerce regulations in Egypt. This is particularly relevant given the growing importance of online sales channels in the furniture sector.

In summary, the significance of this research lies in its ability to address a gap in the literature, provide practical insights for furniture e-retailers and manufacturers, contribute to the understanding of e-commerce adoption in developing economies, and potentially inform policy decisions related to the digital transformation of the furniture industry in Egypt.

2.8. Case Study: Homzmart.com

Homzmart.com serves as the case study for this research. As an online furniture retailer in Egypt, Homzmart represents the intersection of traditional furniture retail and e-commerce. By examining Homzmart's operations and consumer interactions, this study aims to provide insights

that are both theoretically grounded and practically applicable to the Egyptian furniture industry's digital transformation.

3. Literature Review

Kotler, et al.(2017), in their book “Marketing 4.0” stated that a new class of consumers is globally emerging: young, urban, middle-class with strong mobility and connectivity. The tendency to mobile is the main distinguishing factor between this new breed of consumers. Their life is moving fast; thus, everything has to be instant and time-efficient. When they are interested in anything, they search for them on their mobile or any device connected to the internet, research price, and quality reviews before purchase. Purchase decisions could be decided anywhere and anytime (Kotler, et al., 2017). By considering such changes, the furniture sellers in Egypt, whether having a virtual store already or want to have a virtual store as an additional distribution channel along with a traditional one, need to understand the influencing factors on online purchase intention.

In this section, the researcher illustrated the factors influencing consumer purchase intention when buying from an online platform. The researcher did not find any paper about the influencing factors on the consumer’s purchase intention when purchasing furniture from an online platform. However, this section illustrated the various factors that influence the purchase intention from an online platform. This section includes the results of the examinations done on the influencing factors previously mentioned in terms of the relationship with the purchase intention and its importance among other influencing factors.

The flow of this section is as below:

- 3.1. [The Attributes Of Online Shopping And E-Service Quality](#)
- 3.2. [Illustration Of The Influencing Factors On Consumers’ Purchase Intention From An Online Platform](#)
- 3.3. [The Visuals As An Influencing Dimension On Online Purchase Intention](#)
- 3.4. [The Consumer Perceived Risk](#)
- 3.5. [Supply Chain Performance And Its Influence On Consumer Purchase Intention](#)
- 3.6. [Dimensions And Criteria Of The Influencing Factors On Online Purchase Intention](#)
- 3.7. [Furniture Industry and E-commerce: Bridging the Literature Gap](#)
- 3.8. [Summery And Consolidation Of Influencing Factors On Online Purchase Intention](#)
- 3.9. [Research Gap](#)
- 3.10. [Research Problem & Objectives](#)
- 3.11. [Major Research Question & Minor Research Questions](#)

3.1. The Attributes of Online Shopping and E-Service Quality

Online shopping has revolutionized the retail landscape, offering consumers unprecedented convenience and access to a vast array of products. E-service quality, a critical factor in the

success of online retailers, encompasses various attributes that contribute to customer satisfaction and loyalty in the digital marketplace (Parasuraman et al., 2005).

The e-service quality is defined as the overall consumers' evaluation of the online retail & e-commerce platform and the consumer's judgment about the electronic platform's quality excellence in e-service and delivery (Lee & Lin, 2006). SERVQUAL scale is widely used to measure the quality of services in different industries. Using the SERVQUAL model to measure the web-based service quality is facing challenges due to its differences compared to the traditional customer service in offline retail. Accordingly, it is vital to understand the online shopping attributes to examine their relationship with overall e-service quality and its impact on the consumers' purchase intention, purchase decision, satisfaction, and loyalty (Lee & Lin, 2006) (Ladhar, 2010) (Kotler, et al., 2017).

Many studies have examined online shopping attributes and classified these attributes into four pillars (Park & Kim, 2003):

- Product range and merchandise,
- Customer service and promotions,
- Website surfing and convenience,
- And security.

These attributes influence the consumers' online purchase journey. Developing the quality of these attributes under the umbrella of e-service quality is the way to improve the consumers' journey when buying from online platforms (Rita, et al., 2019).

3.1.1. Product range and merchandise:

The digital revolution has fundamentally altered the retail environment, with online shopping emerging as a predominant influence on the consumer market. A primary advantage of e-commerce, especially in the furniture sector, is the extensive and varied selection of products accessible to consumers. In contrast to conventional brick-and-mortar establishments limited by spatial constraints, online platforms provide a vast array of products, accommodating diverse consumer tastes and promoting competitive pricing (Chen, et al., 2016).

This extensive product assortment is illustrated by e-commerce leaders such as Amazon, which have transformed the methods by which individuals seek and acquire products. The broad array of internet possibilities accommodates varied consumer preferences and permits online retailers to generally maintain reduced overhead expenses, allowing them to provide competitive prices that appeal to price-sensitive consumers (Chen, et al., 2016).

The plethora of alternatives might be daunting without adequate organization and presentation. The significance of product-related attributes, such as comprehensive and exceptional product information, is paramount. In the furniture industry, where tactile encounters are key, the conveyance of precise product details, high-quality images, 360-degree views, and augmented reality features can bridge the virtual and physical purchasing experiences (Park & Kim, 2003); (Ladhar, 2010); (Kotler, et al., 2017); (Yu, 2017). This extensive information not only helps

decision-making but also alleviates the perceived hazards of purchasing furniture online without human evaluation.

Additionally, the digital landscape facilitates advanced search and filtering capabilities, enabling customers to rapidly traverse extensive product catalogs and compare things to choose solutions that correspond with their requirements, preferences, and financial limitations (Park & Kim, 2003). The integration of a diverse product selection and comprehensive information fosters a robust ecosystem that improves the purchasing experience, turning furniture buying from a daunting endeavor into an enjoyable, informative, and convenient activity.

The advancement of e-commerce in the furniture business is anticipated to heighten the focus on improving these characteristics, confirming online shopping as the preferred method for obtaining furniture and home design (Yu, 2017). The capacity to access a wide range of choices, together with the convenience and customization provided by digital platforms, will persist in propelling the expansion of online furniture sales. Nonetheless, e-commerce companies must strike a careful equilibrium between product diversity and efficient information delivery to guarantee a smooth and gratifying shopping experience for their clientele.

3.1.2. Customer service and promotions:

The online shopping scene, especially in the furniture sector, has been profoundly influenced by the combination of vast product assortments and efficient customer service. Chen et al. (2016) emphasize that online platforms provide a broader selection of products than traditional stores, frequently at competitive rates owing to lower overhead expenses. This advantage is especially evident in furniture retail, as the limitations of physical showroom space are removed, enabling buyers to examine various styles, materials, and price ranges from the convenience of their homes.

Nonetheless, the efficacy of online furniture selling is not exclusively reliant on product diversity. The caliber of customer service is vital, particularly for high-involvement products such as furniture. Rita et al. (2019) assert that responsive contact channels, explicit return rules, and tailored support markedly improve e-service quality. These components are especially significant in the absence of in-person interactions that often define furniture shopping experiences.

The significance of customer care during the online shopping experience is paramount. As observed by Park & Kim (2003), Ladhar (2010), and Kotler et al. (2017), it is vital for online retailers to fulfill the requirement for interaction by providing communication options that are easy to use, rapid in response, and efficient. This is particularly vital when addressing products such as furniture, where consumers frequently have particular inquiries regarding size, materials, or customization alternatives.

Furthermore, the digital landscape facilitates advanced search and filtering capabilities, allowing consumers to traverse extensive product catalogs with efficiency. The simplicity of navigation, along with the capacity to juxtapose products, enables consumers to make decisions that align with their requirements, preferences, and financial limitations (Park & Kim, 2003). The delivery of comprehensive, high-quality product information facilitates the decision-making process,

alleviating the perceived hazards linked to purchasing furniture online without personal examination.

To augment the client experience and stimulate sales, internet shops frequently utilize diverse promotional methods. Park & Kim (2003) emphasize the efficacy of discounts, loyalty programs, and seasonal promotions in attracting and retaining customers. The integration of these tactics with exceptional customer service and an extensive product assortment formulates a persuasive value proposition for online furniture consumers.

The combination of a vast product assortment, comprehensive information, and exceptional customer service fosters a robust ecosystem that improves the whole shopping experience. It converts the process of furniture shopping from a potentially daunting endeavor into an enjoyable, instructive, and convenient experience. As e-commerce advances, especially within the furniture sector, the emphasis on enhancing these elements will probably increase, further establishing online purchasing as the favored approach for acquiring furniture and home decor (Yu, 2017).

3.1.3. Website Surfing and Convenience

The evolution of e-commerce has transformed the retail sector, especially within the furniture business, by providing consumers with an exceptional shopping experience marked by vast product selections, improved customer service, and intuitive interfaces. Online platforms possess a significant advantage over conventional brick-and-mortar establishments, since they may display an extensive range of products without the limitations of physical showroom space. This enables clients to examine a varied array of styles, materials, and price ranges from the convenience of their residences (Chen, et al., 2016).

The convenience of accessing an e-commerce website plays a key role in the whole purchasing experience. Lee & Lin (2006) assert that intuitive design, rapid loading speeds, and mobile responsiveness are essential elements that enhance user happiness. Furniture retailers may greatly improve buyer convenience by offering comprehensive product information, high-resolution photos, and virtual space planning tools.

The website or mobile application functions as the consumer's online purchasing platform, rendering the e-store's appearance, organization, electronic features, and user-friendliness essential determinants of perceived quality. An effectively designed e-store diminishes consumers' perceived costs and time associated with seeking product information and processing it, therefore reducing the effort required to select and purchase a product (Park & Kim, 2003); (Ladhar, 2010); (Kotler, et al., 2017).

The broad product range available online is a crucial aspect in attracting consumers. E-commerce leaders have established new benchmarks in product diversity, addressing a broad range of consumer interests. Furthermore, the diminished administrative expenses linked to online retail frequently result in competitive pricing, which is especially attractive to cost-sensitive consumers (Chen, et al., 2016).

However, the success of online furniture selling isn't exclusively based on product diversity and website accessibility. The caliber of customer service is essential, particularly for high-involvement products such as furniture. Efficient customer service is essential for improving the online shopping experience. Responsive contact channels, clear return rules, and individualized support considerably increase e-service quality (Rita, et al., 2019). These components are especially crucial in the absence of in-person interactions that often define furniture shopping experiences.

To augment the client experience and stimulate sales, internet shops frequently utilize diverse promotional methods. These encompass discounts, loyalty programs, and seasonal promotions, which have demonstrated efficacy in attracting and retaining customers (Park & Kim, 2003). When integrated with exceptional customer service, an extensive product assortment, and an intuitive interface, these methods formulate a persuasive value proposition for online furniture consumers.

The combination of a vast product selection, comprehensive information, exceptional customer service, and user-friendly website design forms a robust ecosystem that improves the whole shopping experience. It converts furniture shopping from a potentially daunting endeavor into an interesting, instructive, and convenient experience. As e-commerce progresses, especially within the furniture sector, the emphasis on enhancing these elements will probably increase, thereby reinforcing online shopping as the favored approach for acquiring furniture and home design (Yu, 2017).

3.1.4. Security and privacy:

The e-commerce environment has been profoundly influenced by several variables affecting consumer behavior, with security and privacy emerging as essential factors in the online shopping experience. This feature of Internet retail is particularly essential as it directly affects consumers' trust and their desire to engage in digital transactions.

A prominent subject in e-commerce research is the perceived risk linked to financial transactions and the safeguarding of personal information. Park & Kim (2003), Ladhar (2010), and Kotler et al. (2017) collectively assert that when e-retailers adopt stringent security measures and supportive protection policies, they establish a secure online shopping environment that markedly enhances consumers' likelihood of making purchase decisions. This underlines the significance of not just installing technical safeguards but also explicitly presenting these steps to potential clients.

The necessity of security in online buying is further underscored by Kim et al. (2008), who remark that e-commerce transactions entail sensitive personal and financial information. As such, the deployment of solid security measures and transparent communication of privacy rules are crucial for developing trust with clients. This factor is particularly significant in nascent e-commerce economies like Egypt, where customers may possess limited familiarity with online buying methods and hence exhibit greater caution in participating in digital transactions.

Rita et al. (2019) have made substantial contributions to the comprehension of online purchasing qualities by formulating a comprehensive model that synthesizes findings from multiple research

investigations. Their model, depicted in Figure 4 and elaborated in Table 2 of their study, analyzes the complex interconnections among customer happiness, customer trust, repurchase intention, word of mouth, and site revisit. This comprehensive approach gives useful insights into how multiple facets of the online buying experience, including security and privacy, interact to influence consumer behavior.

The significance of security and privacy in e-commerce transcends the immediate transaction. It is essential for establishing enduring relationships with clients and cultivating loyalty. When consumers see their personal and financial information as secure, they are more inclined to make repeat purchases, endorse the e-retailer to others, and return to the site for subsequent transactions. This ripple effect highlights the strategic significance of investing in comprehensive security measures and transparent privacy rules.

Furthermore, as the e-commerce sector progresses, especially within the furniture business, the emphasis on security and privacy is expected to increase. Yu et al. (2017) emphasize the increasing significance of e-commerce logistics in supply chain management, which inevitably entails the management of sensitive consumer information. Consequently, online furniture merchants must address both the security of financial transactions and the privacy concerns associated with their logistics and supply chain operations.

In summary, security and privacy are fundamental elements in online buying, significantly affecting consumer trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. As e-commerce continues to expand and evolve, particularly in emerging economies and specialist industries like furniture shopping, the emphasis on these traits is likely to rise, impacting the strategies and practices of successful online merchants.

Figure 4: Model that has been tested by Rita, et al.(2019) to examine the relationship among customer satisfaction, customer trust, repurchase intention, word of mouth, and site revisit.

General access

Source: (Rita, et al., 2019)

Table 2: Table shows the four dimensions of online shipping and the factors related to each dimension and items related to each factor examined in other research.

Constructs		Items	Source
Website Design	Information Quality	IQ1. The information on the website is pretty much what I need to carry out my tasks.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		IQ2. The website adequately meets my information needs.	
		IQ3. The information on the website is effective.	
	Website Aesthetics	WA1. The website is visually pleasing.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		WA2. The website displays a visually pleasing design.	
		WA3. The website is visually appealing.	
	Purchase Process	PP1. The website has no difficulties with making a payment online	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		PP2. The purchasing process was not difficult.	
		PP3. It is easier to use the website to complete my business with the company than to use a telephone, fax or mail a representative.	
	Website Convenience	WC1. The website displays visually pleasing easy to read content.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		WC2. The text on the website is easy to read.	
		WC3. The website labels are easy to understand.	
	Product Selection	PS1. All my business with the company can be completed via the website.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		PS2. This website has a good selection.	
		PS3. The site has a wide variety of products that interest me.	
	Price Offerings	PO1. The website offers discounts or free shipping.	Blut (2016); Holloway
		PO2. The website has low prices.	

General access

		PO3. The website has lower prices than offline stores.	and Beatty (2008)
	<i>Website Personalization</i>	WP1. The website allows me to interact with it to receive tailored information.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		WP2. The website has interactive features, which help me accomplish my task.	
		WP3. I can interact with the website in order to get information tailored to my specific needs.	
	<i>System Availability</i>	SA1. When I use the website, there is very little waiting time between my actions and the website's response.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		SA2. The website loads quickly.	
		SA3. The website takes a long time to load. (R)	
Customer Service	<i>Service Level</i>	SL1. The online shop provides a telephone number to reach the company.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		SL2. The online shop has customer service representatives available online.	
		SL3. The online shop offers the ability to speak to a live person if there is a problem.	
	<i>Return Handling/Policies</i>	RP1. The online shop provides me with convenient options for returning items.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		RP2. The online shop handles product returns well.	
		RP3. The online shop offers a meaningful guarantee.	
Security/ Privacy	<i>Security</i>	SC1. I feel safe in my transactions with the online shop.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		SC2. The online shop has adequate security features.	
		SC3. This site protects information about my credit card.	
	<i>Privacy</i>	PR1. I trust the online shop to keep my personal information safe.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		PR2. I trust the website administrators will not misuse my personal information.	
		PR3. It protects information about my web-shopping behavior.	
Fulfillment	<i>Timeliness of Delivery</i>	TD1. The product is delivered by the time promised by the company.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		TD2. This online shop website makes items available for delivery within a suitable time frame.	
		TD3. It quickly delivers what I order.	
	<i>Order Accuracy</i>	OA1. You get what you ordered from this website.	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		OA2. The website sends out the items ordered.	
		OA3. The website is truthful about its offerings.	
	<i>Delivery Condition</i>	DC1. The product was damaged during delivery. (R)	Blut (2016); Holloway and Beatty (2008)
		DC2. The ordered products arrived in good condition.	
		DC3. The products arrived with major damage. (R)	
Overall e-Service Quality		SQ1. Overall. My purchase experience with this online shop is excellent	Blut (2016)
		SQ2. The overall quality of the service provided by this online shop is excellent	
		SQ3. My overall feelings toward this online shop are very satisfied	

Customer Satisfaction	S1. I am satisfied with this online shop.	Fornell (1992)
	S2. The online shop is getting close to the ideal online retailer.	
	S3. The online shop always meets my needs.	
Customer Trust	T1. One can expect good advice from this online shop.*	Gefen (2002); Lee and Turban (2001); Urban et al. (2009)
	T2. This online shop is genuinely interested in customer welfare.	
	T3. If problems arise, one can expect to be treated fairly by this online shop.	
	T4. I am happy with the standards by which this online shop is operating.	
	T5. This online shop operates scrupulously.	
	T6. You can believe the statements of this online shop.	
Re-purchase Intention	RI1. I will make more purchases through this online shop in the future.	Zeithaml et al. (1996)
	RI2. I will increase purchases through this online shop.	
	RI3. I will intensify purchases through this online shop.	
Word of Mouth	WOM1. I say positive things about this online shop to other people.	Zeithaml et al. (1996)
	WOM2. I recommend this online shop to anyone who seeks my advice.	
	WOM3. I encourage friends and others to purchase goods from this online shop.	
Site Revisit	SR1. I will not shop again from this online shop. (R)*	Gounaris et al. (2010)
	SR2. I will make my next purchase from this online shop.	
	SR3. I will re-visit this online shop in the future.	

Source: (Rita, et al., 2019)

3.2. Illustration of The Influencing Factors on Consumers' Purchase Intention From An Online Platform

The rapid expansion of global e-commerce necessitates an understanding of the key characteristics that influence customer intent to purchase via online platforms. Kennedy and Kundu (2018) presented a compilation of determinants affecting online purchase intention, which were subsequently analyzed by other scholars as follows:

3.2.1. Product Availability and Selection

Product availability and selection are crucial factors that significantly influence consumer intention to buy products or services online. Kennedy and Kundu (2018) emphasize that if an online platform fails to satisfy the consumer's need by making the desired product or service available, it negatively impacts the likelihood of return visits to the platform. This is particularly relevant in the context of online furniture retail, where consumers often seek specific styles, designs, or functionalities to match their home decor or personal preferences.

Chen et al. (2016) further highlight that a broad selection of products can significantly enhance the consumer's shopping experience and increase purchase intention. In the furniture industry, this could translate to offering a wide range of styles (e.g., modern, traditional, rustic), materials

(e.g., wood, metal, glass), and price points to cater to diverse consumer preferences. Moreover, the ability to customize or personalize furniture items can be a strong differentiator for online retailers, potentially increasing consumer engagement and purchase intention (Pappas, 2017).

For online furniture retailers in Egypt, ensuring a diverse and well-curated product range that reflects local tastes while also introducing international trends could be a key strategy to attract and retain customers. Additionally, maintaining accurate inventory information and clearly communicating stock availability can help manage customer expectations and reduce the likelihood of abandoned purchases due to out-of-stock situations (Jain, 2017).

3.2.2. Pricing and Promotional Strategies

The pricing of products on online platforms plays a vital role in shaping purchase intentions, often serving as a primary factor in consumers' decision-making process. Kennedy and Kundu (2018) suggest that competitive pricing can significantly influence consumers, encouraging repetitive visits to the online platform that offers such pricing, which in turn leads to repetitive purchasing behavior. In the context of furniture retail, where items are often considered high-involvement purchases, pricing strategies become even more critical.

Online furniture retailers must strike a balance between offering competitive prices and maintaining profit margins. This can be achieved through various strategies such as dynamic pricing, bundle deals, or tiered pricing based on product features or quality. Additionally, promotional activities such as discounts, vouchers, and loyalty programs have been identified as strong influencers driving online sales (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018). These strategies not only attract price-sensitive customers but also create a sense of urgency or exclusivity that can prompt purchases.

For the Egyptian market, where e-commerce is still evolving, transparent pricing strategies coupled with attractive promotions could be key to building trust and encouraging consumers to make high-value furniture purchases online. Seasonal sales, festive offers, or limited-time discounts aligned with local cultural events could be particularly effective in driving traffic and conversions. Moreover, implementing a loyalty program that rewards repeat customers can foster long-term relationships and increase customer lifetime value (Kang, 2014).

3.2.3. Comparison Capabilities

One of the significant advantages of online purchasing is the ability to compare products or services across various dimensions such as specifications, prices, quality, availability, and promotional offers. This comparison capability saves the consumer's time and money, making it a crucial factor in influencing purchase intentions (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018). In the context of furniture retail, this feature becomes particularly important due to the high-involvement nature of furniture purchases.

Online furniture retailers can leverage this consumer behavior by providing comprehensive product information and easy-to-use comparison tools. This could include side-by-side product comparisons, highlighting key features, materials, dimensions, and price points. Additionally,

offering user-generated content such as customer reviews and ratings for each product can provide valuable insights for potential buyers, further aiding their decision-making process (Erkan, 2016).

For the Egyptian market, where consumers might be transitioning from traditional brick-and-mortar furniture shopping to online platforms, robust comparison capabilities can serve as a significant differentiator. By offering detailed product information, high-quality images from multiple angles, and even 3D visualization tools, online retailers can help bridge the gap between physical and digital shopping experiences. This not only enhances the user experience but also builds confidence in making large purchases online, potentially increasing conversion rates (Bleier, 2019).

3.2.4. Customer Service Quality

The quality of customer service and the clarity of policies, regulations, and frequently asked questions significantly impact consumer comfort and confidence in completing an online purchase (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018). For online furniture retailers, providing comprehensive product information, responsive customer support, and clear policies regarding returns and exchanges can greatly enhance consumer trust and purchase intention.

In the furniture retail context, where products are often large, expensive, and require assembly, exceptional customer service becomes even more critical. This could include offering pre-sale consultations to help customers choose the right furniture for their needs, providing detailed assembly instructions or video tutorials, and offering post-purchase support for any issues that may arise (Parasuraman, 2005).

For the Egyptian market, where online furniture shopping might be a relatively new concept for many consumers, robust customer service can play a crucial role in building trust and encouraging first-time purchases. This could involve offering multiple channels for customer support (e.g., phone, email, live chat), providing service in local languages, and ensuring quick response times to queries and concerns. Additionally, implementing a hassle-free return and exchange policy, while challenging for bulky items like furniture, can significantly reduce perceived risk and increase purchase intention (Orel, 2014).

3.2.5. Website Design and User Experience

The aesthetics and functionality of the website play a crucial role in influencing purchase intentions. Belal (2019) and Rita et al. (2019) emphasize the importance of website design in the online shopping experience. For furniture retailers, this includes aspects such as high-quality product images, 3D visualization tools, and intuitive navigation that can significantly enhance the user experience and increase purchase likelihood.

A well-designed website should provide a seamless and enjoyable shopping experience, from product discovery to checkout. This involves creating an intuitive navigation structure, implementing effective search and filter functionalities, and ensuring fast loading times across all devices. For furniture retailers, incorporating features like room planners, augmented reality

(AR) tools that allow customers to visualize furniture in their own spaces, or virtual showrooms can significantly enhance the shopping experience and reduce uncertainty associated with online furniture purchases (Yim, 2017).

In the Egyptian context, where internet speeds and device capabilities may vary, it's crucial to optimize the website for performance across different conditions. This could involve implementing progressive loading techniques, offering a mobile-optimized version of the site, and ensuring that key functionalities are accessible even on lower-end devices. Additionally, considering local design preferences and cultural nuances in the website's aesthetic can help create a more engaging and relatable user experience for Egyptian consumers (Hasan, 2016).

3.2.6. Trust and Security Perceptions

Trust is a critical factor in online purchase intentions, especially for high-value items like furniture. Chen et al. (2016) identify trust as one of the key dimensions influencing online purchase intention. This includes perceptions of the online platform's reliability, privacy policies, and security measures for financial transactions. For furniture retailers, building trust through transparent business practices, secure payment gateways, and positive customer reviews can significantly impact purchase intentions.

In the context of online furniture retail, where customers are often making significant financial commitments without physically interacting with the product, trust becomes paramount. Retailers can build trust by providing detailed and accurate product descriptions, offering virtual consultations with design experts, and implementing a transparent and fair return policy. Additionally, showcasing customer testimonials, before-and-after photos of furnished spaces, and user-generated content can help potential buyers feel more confident in their purchase decisions (Kim, 2017).

For the Egyptian market, where e-commerce is still gaining traction, addressing security concerns is crucial. This could involve partnering with reputable payment gateways, implementing SSL certificates for secure transactions, and clearly communicating the measures taken to protect customer data. Moreover, offering cash-on-delivery options or partnering with local banks for installment plans could help alleviate concerns about online payments and make high-value furniture purchases more accessible to a broader audience (El-Masry, 2016).

3.2.7. Delivery and Logistics

The efficiency and reliability of delivery services have a substantial impact on purchase intentions in online retail. Kennedy and Kundu (2018) found that both delivery fees and delivery time significantly influence purchase intention. For furniture retailers, offering flexible delivery options, clear communication about delivery timelines, and efficient handling of large items can positively influence consumer decisions.

In the furniture industry, where products are often bulky and require special handling, the logistics process becomes even more critical. Online retailers need to ensure they have robust partnerships with reliable shipping companies that can handle furniture deliveries efficiently and safely. Offering services like white-glove delivery, where items are not only delivered but also

assembled and installed in the customer's home, can be a significant value-add that influences purchase decisions (Rao, 2011).

For the Egyptian market, where addresses might not always be standardized and traffic conditions can be unpredictable, implementing an efficient delivery system is crucial. This could involve partnering with local logistics companies familiar with the terrain, offering real-time tracking of deliveries, and providing flexible delivery windows to accommodate customers' schedules. Additionally, considering the option of pick-up points or partnerships with local furniture stores for product viewing and collection could provide alternatives that cater to different customer preferences and address potential delivery challenges in certain areas (Agatz, 2008).

3.2.8. Visual Merchandising

In the context of online furniture retail, visual elements play a crucial role in purchase intentions. Mazurova (2017) highlights the importance of brand presentation, color schemes, and product positioning on websites. Effective use of these visual elements can attract consumer attention and positively influence their purchase decisions.

For furniture retailers, visual merchandising extends beyond just product photos. It involves creating an immersive online shopping experience that helps customers envision how the furniture will look and function in their own spaces. This can be achieved through high-quality, zoomable product images from multiple angles, lifestyle shots showing the furniture in styled room settings, and even 360-degree product views or virtual reality experiences (Bleier, 2019).

In the Egyptian market, where traditional bazaars and showrooms have long been the primary means of furniture shopping, translating the tactile and visual experience of in-person shopping to the digital realm is crucial. This could involve incorporating elements of local design aesthetics in the website's visual presentation, showcasing furniture in settings that resonate with Egyptian home styles, and using color schemes that appeal to local preferences. Additionally, featuring locally made or designed furniture prominently can tap into national pride and support for local craftsmanship, potentially influencing purchase decisions (Mostafa, 2006).

3.2.9. Mobile Accessibility

With the increasing use of mobile devices for online shopping, the mobile accessibility of e-commerce platforms has become a significant factor in purchase intentions. Kotler et al. (2017) note that purchase decisions can be made anywhere and anytime, emphasizing the need for furniture retailers to optimize their online platforms for mobile users.

For furniture retailers, this means ensuring that their websites are not just mobile-responsive, but truly mobile-optimized. This involves designing for smaller screens without sacrificing functionality or visual appeal, implementing touch-friendly interfaces, and ensuring that all features - from product browsing to checkout - work seamlessly on mobile devices. Additionally, developing native mobile apps can provide an even more streamlined and personalized shopping experience, potentially increasing engagement and purchase likelihood (Wang, 2015).

In the Egyptian context, where mobile internet usage is high and often the primary means of accessing the internet for many users, prioritizing mobile accessibility is crucial. This could involve optimizing for popular local mobile devices and operating systems, ensuring fast loading times even on slower mobile networks, and perhaps even offering mobile-exclusive deals or features to encourage adoption of mobile shopping for furniture. Moreover, integrating with popular mobile payment systems or offering mobile wallet options can further streamline the purchase process and potentially increase conversion rates among mobile users ((MCIT), 2021).

In conclusion, the factors influencing consumers' purchase intention from online platforms are multifaceted and interconnected. For online furniture retailers in Egypt, understanding and effectively addressing these factors can significantly enhance their ability to attract and convert potential customers. As the e-commerce landscape continues to evolve, particularly in emerging markets like Egypt, ongoing research and adaptation to changing consumer preferences will be crucial for success in the online furniture retail sector. By focusing on product availability, competitive pricing, effective visual merchandising, robust customer service, and mobile optimization, furniture e-tailers can create a compelling online shopping experience that meets the unique needs and preferences of Egyptian consumers.

3.3. The Visuals as an Influencing Dimension on Online Purchase Intention

In her paper, Elena Mazurova (2017) examined three factors that influence consumer purchase intention. These three factors are under the dimension of "Visual"; the brand, the website's color, and the product position on the website's screen (Mazurova, 2017). Mazurova (2017) created a computer experiment to examine the importance of these three influencing factors. This computer experiment consists of a different consecutive combination of 6 colors, 4 product positions, and four brands, giving 96 possible combinations.

3.3.1. The Visuals as an Influencing Dimension on Online Purchase Intention

Visual elements play a crucial role in shaping consumers' purchase intentions in the online shopping environment. Elena Mazurova's (2017) research provides valuable insights into three key visual factors that significantly influence consumer behavior in e-commerce: brand presentation, color schemes, and product positioning on the website.

Mazurova (2017) conducted a comprehensive computer experiment to evaluate the importance of these visual factors. The experiment involved a series of 96 possible combinations, created by varying 6 colors, 4 product positions, and four brands. This methodical approach allowed for a thorough examination of how these visual elements interact and impact consumer purchase intentions.

3.3.2. The Brand Influence on Online Purchase Intention

The brand emerges as the most influential factor in Mazurova's (2017) study, highlighting its critical role in shaping consumer perceptions and purchase decisions in the online environment. A brand transcends mere visual representation, such as a logo or name, to become a powerful emotional and psychological construct in the consumer's mind.

Key aspects of brand influence include:

1. **Emotional Connection:** Brands address consumers' feelings and emotions, creating a subconscious bond that can significantly impact purchase decisions.
2. **Memory Retention:** Strong brands are easily remembered, helping e-retailers differentiate themselves in a crowded marketplace.
3. **Information Shortcut:** Well-known brands can compensate for limited product information, serving as a proxy for quality and reliability.
4. **Attention Grabber:** Recognized brands naturally attract consumer attention during online shopping sessions.
5. **Information Aggregator:** Brands accumulate and convey information through various channels, including promotional activities, word-of-mouth communication, and consumers' previous experiences.

Mazurova's (2017) experiment conclusively demonstrated that brand attributes were the most influential factor in determining consumers' purchase intentions, underscoring the importance of strong brand development and presentation in e-commerce strategies.

3.3.3. The Color Influence on Online Purchase Intention

Color emerged as the second most important visual factor in Mazurova's (2017) study, albeit with approximately half the impact of brand influence. The perception and impact of color in e-commerce are nuanced and can vary significantly based on several factors:

1. **Individual Differences:** Color perception and preferences can be influenced by a person's education, personal tastes, and life experiences.
2. **Cultural Factors:** Different cultures may associate colors with varying meanings or emotions, affecting their impact on purchase intentions.
3. **Demographic Variations:** Gender and age can play a role in color preferences and their influence on buying decisions.
4. **Context Sensitivity:** The effectiveness of color schemes may depend on the type of product being sold and the overall design of the e-commerce platform.

While color proved less influential than brand in Mazurova's (2017) experiment, its significant impact highlights the importance of thoughtful color selection in e-commerce website design. Retailers should consider their target audience's preferences and cultural context when developing their color strategies.

3.3.4. The Product Position on the Website and its Influence on Online Purchase Intention

Product positioning on the website, while ranking third in importance among the visual factors studied by Mazurova (2017), still plays a significant role in influencing consumer behavior. This finding aligns with research from Google and the University of Tulsa, emphasizing the importance of strategic product placement in e-commerce.

Key considerations for product positioning include:

1. **The Golden Triangle Area:** This concept refers to the top-left corner of a webpage, where consumers typically begin their visual scan. Products placed in this area are more likely to catch the consumer's attention.
2. **Eye Movement Patterns:** Consumers tend to scan web pages from the upper left corner, moving downward and to the right. This "F-shaped" pattern of eye movement influences how products are perceived and interacted with on the page.
3. **Limited Attention Span:** Google research indicates that consumers typically spend only a few seconds scanning a webpage. This brief window emphasizes the need for impactful product presentation and positioning.
4. **Strategic Product Placement:** Marketers can leverage understanding of eye movement patterns to strategically position products. For example, less popular items might be placed among more popular ones to increase their visibility.

While product positioning ranked third in Mazurova's (2017) study, its influence should not be underestimated. Effective product placement can significantly enhance the visibility of items and influence consumer purchase decisions.

In conclusion, Mazurova's (2017) research provides valuable insights into the hierarchy of visual factors influencing online purchase intentions. Brand emerges as the most potent influencer, followed by color schemes and product positioning. These findings underscore the importance of a holistic approach to visual design in e-commerce, where brand development, thoughtful color selection, and strategic product placement work in concert to enhance consumer engagement and drive purchase intentions.

For online furniture retailers, particularly those operating in emerging e-commerce markets like Egypt, these insights can inform more effective visual merchandising strategies. By prioritizing brand development, carefully considering color schemes that resonate with local preferences, and optimizing product placement on their websites, furniture e-tailers can create more compelling and influential visual experiences for their customers.

3.4. The Consumer Perceived Risk

Many researchers were concerned about consumer attitude and perceived risk in specific. According to Neilson's study, with the rapid growth of e-commerce and online shopping, security issues have become a key concern (Fatemeh Meskaran, & Bharani, 2013). There is a probability that online shoppers will risk monetary loss due to the unsatisfying product or service in terms of the product or the service is not worth considering the promised quality, or the performance described initially has been in the retailer's website (Ariffin, et al., 2018). One of the most significant limitations for online purchase intention to increase online transactions is building consumer trust and managing the associated risks like security, fraud, authentication, and loss. Consumers consider online shopping as riskier than offline shopping, providing that physical shopping is more satisfying where the product or service is tangible before the purchase is made (Fatemeh Meskaran, & Bharani, 2013). Accordingly, the consumer perceived risks are influencing the consumer attitude, which will reflect on the online shopping's behavior (Arif, et al., 2014)

Table 3: Ranking the different types of risks perceived by online shoppers

Rank	Type of Perceived Risk	Observations
1	Financial risk	This highest perceived risk. Due to the fear of suffering from a financial loss as a cause of the fraud of electronic payment
2	Performance risk	The 2 nd , and it is mainly about the product performance and the fear of not meeting the consumer expectations or not matching the displayed description on the retailer's website
3	Time risk	It is linked to the performance risk, as the consumer here has fears about the time consumed to get an unsatisfying product and to return it back
4	Delivery risk	Consumer perceived risk here is all about overall delivery performance in terms of time and the safe package without any damages
5	Privacy risk	The fear of misuse of consumer's private data like credit card details
6	Psychological risk	Consumer's fear when doubting the electronic transactions, especially with an urgent need of a product or with an expensive product
7	Social risk	The fear of being blamed by referent groups (Friends or Family members), mostly if the process was not satisfactory or occurrence of any other risks

Source: (Arif, et al., 2014)

Ariffin, Mohan, and Goh (2018), in their research paper, examined the relationship between the online purchase intention as a dependent variable and six out of seven risks as independent variables (Financial risk, Product risk, Security risk, Time risk, Social risk, and Psychological risk), and the results as below:

- **Financial risk** has a negative relationship with online purchase intention. It has the most significant influence on products purchased from online platforms—this finding aligned with other research done on this factor even with different sample characteristics.
- **Product risk** also has a negative relationship with online purchase intention. The definition of product risk is the product's failure to meet the promised performance—this finding aligned with other research done on this factor but different sample characteristics.
- **Security risk** has a negative relationship with online purchase intention. The definition of security risk is the potential loss due to cyberattack, hacking, or fraud while doing transactions through the internet. On the third of July 2020, SWVL, an Egyptian operator for bus routes and bus-booking applications operating in Egypt, Kenya, and Pakistan, has been struck by a data breach. The breached data were restricted to consumers' contact details and no effect on passwords or credit card details (Views, 2020). Such incidents strengthen consumer fears about security risks.
- **Time risk** has a negative relationship with online purchase intention. Time risk is the time consumed for a buyer to find the desired product, browse for online information about it, purchase it, and wait for the online retailer's delivery. Accordingly, if the online shopping journey is simple with precise details about the product or service, consumers tend to decide.
- **Social risk** is not related to online purchase intention. This result is contrary to previous research that recorded a negative relationship between social risk and online purchase intention. Family members or friends will not negatively judge the buyer due to a

dissatisfying purchase decision or even a brand choice. It also shows that the purchase decision is solely the buyer to buy from an online shop.

- **Psychological risk** has a negative relationship with online purchase intention. This risk is the consumer's disappointment in making a poor selection of a product or service against other available opportunities before the purchase decision. The buyers will fear getting disappointed and frustrated if the received product is ordered online in lousy quality due to improper packaging, or the product was not meeting expectations as the received product does not match what has been displayed online on the retailer's platform. Another psychological risk where the buyer may be at risk of getting addicted to buying from online platforms offers continuous eye-catching offers and discounts.

3.5. Supply Chain Performance and Its Influence On Consumer Purchase Intention

The retail supply chain has lately started to attract academics with open problems about the complexity of operations and inventory management. It also noted that the retail industry reached a point of the "bullwhip" effect that can cause chaos on the rest of the supply chain due to its fluctuating nature (Ekinci & Baykasoglu, 2015). Supply chain operations and challenges are similar in any retail sector. Based on the analysis, it consists of the below points (Ekinci & Baykasoglu, 2015):

- **Marketing Channels:** Multiple locations for marketing like physical stores and/or an online store
- **Number of Stores:** The number of running physical or virtual stores
- **Store Types:** Different sizes (e.g., hypermarket, express market, convenience stores, supermarket), brands, concepts, or activities
- **Product Nature:** Seasonal products, food & beverage items
- **SKU and Supplier Complexity:** The number of SKUs and suppliers directly impacts supply chain planning complexity
- **SKU Interactions:** SKUs that complement or substitute each other, and how they interact (e.g., coffee and coffee creamer, furniture and fittings)
- **Physical Characteristics:** Size, weight, and fragility of SKUs requiring special handling (e.g., furniture, fragile products)
- **Pricing Strategy:** Pricing strategy that influences sales turnover of individual SKUs
- **Merchandising:** SKU display, assortment, and shelf positioning
- **Private Label vs. Branded SKUs:** Management of private label and branded SKUs
- **Supply Chain Network:** Sourcing, distribution, and logistics networks
- **Inventory Management:** Handling of discontinued, slow-moving, leftover, discounted, and outlet SKUs

Supply chain operations directly impact consumer satisfaction and repurchase when buying from an online platform, such as providing the right product, stock availability, quality, packaging, customer service, fast delivery, and prompt reverse flow (Hu, et al., 2015).

The logistics management in the online platforms' supply chain collects the ordered products from different suppliers or manufacturers and stores them in a sorting center or warehouse for quick distribution. After receiving the product in the sorting center, the packaging and labeling (buyer information and invoice) operations occur. Once the package/order is ready for shipping, logistics arrangements consider the destination, distance, and transport mood. This logistics planning is also taking into consideration any reverse flow of return requests. In summary, this logistics flow includes (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018):

- Inventory management
- Vendor management
- Packaging
- Warehousing management (First Mile)
- Forward and reverse flow (Last-Mile Delivery)

In their paper, Kennedy and Kundu (2018) examined the influence of delivery fees and the delivery time on purchase intention. They found that both logistics factors significantly impact purchase intention with a confidence rate of 99%. They also found that offering free of charge delivery services can drive online sales. However, the logistics cost is a factor the business should consider in terms of its price and the party that should bear its cost (the vendor, e-retailers, or the consumer), and the shipping matrix's design. It also highlights the importance of not impacting the service quality due to reducing the logistics cost and increasing the chances of purchase decision by considering the utilization of the operations' resources and optimizing operations to achieve the maximum efficiency (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018).

3.6. Dimensions And Criteria of The Influencing Factors On Online Purchase Intention

Chen, et al. (2016) examined with his team the critical influencing factors on online purchase intention and the casual relationships between them to understand the most influencing factors to simulate the sales. They created four influencing dimensions; Online Service, Convenience, Trust & Risk, and Uncertainty; every dimension has three criteria (see Table 2). They concluded that two factors are critical for improvement; first, the responsiveness, second, the communication and interaction; both influence other factors most. Both factors are related to the customer service quality of the e-retailer and the diversity of communication means and reliability. According to the ranking in "Table 3," five factors are related to consumer perceived risks. In terms of ranking, financial risk is the first and most substantial influencing factor for online purchase intention. Consumers are considering the "trust" (as the second influencing factor) then the risk of their "privacy" (Chen, et al., 2016). "Financial risk" and "Trust" are the most influential factors (Chen, et al., 2016). These three most influential factors were examined by Belal (2019), where Souq and Jumia platforms are the scopes³. The results were also second to the results by Chen and his team (2016), while security and privacy came after "designing the website" and product's information quality (Belal, 2019).

³ Souq and Jumia are the biggest online shopping platforms in Egypt (Belal, 2019)

Table 4: The influencing factors by dimension and criteria on the online purchase intention

Dimensions	Criteria	Criteria Definition	Rank
Online Service	Responsiveness	The accuracy and swiftness of responses	9
	Communication & Interaction	The ability of interaction between customers & the online retailer	7
	Consistency	Delivering the promised specifications of the product as displayed on the website	8
Convenience	Better Prices	Providing the best prices with the ability for price comparison	10
	Time-Saving	The availability of the product all the time and saving the consumer time by providing a user-friendly shopping journey	11
	Broader Selection	Providing more choices for similar products with sufficient and transparent information on the online platform	6
Trust & Risk	Trust	A set of beliefs that makes the e-retailer deserve the consumer's trust, like the reliability of the online platform and the privacy policy	2
	Privacy Risk	It is the fear of providing personal & financial information	3
	Financial Security	The security when providing financial information like credit card details and transaction	1
Uncertainty	Product Risk	The product may not be performing as promised	12
	Delivery Risk	The risk of not delivering the product after the financial transaction	5
	Product Quality	Lacking product quality guarantee	4

Source: (Chen, et al., 2016)

3.7. Furniture Industry and E-commerce: Bridging the Literature Gap

The existing literature on online purchase intentions extensively explores general factors such as e-service quality, visual merchandising, consumer risks, and supply chain performance. However, the specific application of these elements to the furniture industry remains under-researched. This gap is significant given the unique characteristics of furniture as a high-involvement product, requiring tactile interaction, visual assessment, and logistical precision (El Zeiny, 2020).

3.7.1. Contextualizing E-commerce in the Furniture Industry

Several studies highlight the nuances of e-commerce adoption in diverse sectors. For instance, Mazurova (2017) explored the role of visual merchandising, while Parasuraman et al. (2005) and Lee & Lin (2006) examined e-service quality dimensions. Yet, these frameworks lack direct application to the furniture sector, where consumer expectations for augmented reality tools, detailed product specifications, and trust-building mechanisms are paramount (Yu, 2017).

The furniture industry's integration with e-commerce is further complicated by logistical challenges, such as the delivery of bulky items and the need for customer-friendly return policies. These complexities, coupled with cultural preferences and digital literacy levels, make the study of online furniture retail essential for emerging markets like Egypt (Jain, 2017).

3.7.2. Unique Challenges in Furniture E-commerce

Furniture e-commerce combines the physical and digital realms, requiring innovative solutions to replicate the in-store experience online. Kim et al. (2017) emphasize the importance of trust and security in online transactions, which is even more critical for furniture purchases involving high financial commitments. Similarly, Kennedy & Kundu (2018) note that product availability and selection significantly influence purchase intentions. For furniture, this means offering a wide range of customizable options and maintaining accurate inventory data.

3.7.3. Research Gap and Contribution

While studies like Chen et al. (2016) and Rita et al. (2019) provide foundational insights into e-service quality and consumer behavior, their generality limits their applicability to the furniture industry. This research bridges this gap by focusing on Egyptian consumers' online purchase intentions for furniture, evaluating factors like supply chain performance, visual merchandising, and trust-building in e-commerce platforms.

3.8. Summary and Consolidation of Influencing Factors on Online Purchase Intention

In this section, the researcher has consolidated all influencing factors of online purchase intention illustrated in the literature review. This table will help create the model that the researcher will examine the influencing factors on the online purchase intention of furniture in Egypt. (See Table 4). This section also captured the modules that are considered the reference for the conceptual module of this research.

3.8.1. The Summary of All Dimensions of E-Service Quality of the Literature Review

Table 5: Summary and consolidation of influencing factors on online purchase intention

Dimensions	Influencing Factors	Business Role	Influence on Purchase Intention	Source
Online Service	Responsiveness	Customer Service	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016)
	Communication & Interaction	Customer Service	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016)
	Consistency	Customer Service	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016)
	Product Information Quality	Content	Positive	• (Belal, 2019)
Convenience	Better Prices	Marketing & Commercial	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016)
	Time-Saving	Technology & Supply chain	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016) (Belal, 2019)
	Broader Selection	Commercial, Technology & Content	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016)
	Delivery Charge	Marketing & Supply chain	Positive	• (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018)
	Delivery Time	Supply Chain	Positive	• (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018)

General access

Visual	Brand	Marketing	Positive	• (Mazurova, 2017)
	Color	Marketing	Positive	• (Mazurova, 2017)
	Product position on the website	Marketing & Content	Positive	• (Mazurova, 2017)
Website design	Website Aesthetics	Product & Technology	Positive	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)
	Purchase Process	Product, Technology & Operations Excellence Team	Positive	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)
	Website Convenience	Product, Technology & Operations Excellence Team	Positive	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)
	Website Personalization	Product & Technology	Positive	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)
	System Availability	Product & Technology	Positive	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)
Trust & Risk	Trust	Marketing, Customer Service, Supply chain & Technology	Positive, Second influencing factor after Financial Risk	• (Chen, et al., 2016) (Belal, 2019)
	Privacy Risk	Technology	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018) (Belal, 2019)
	Financial Security	Technology	Positive & It has the significance Influence	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018) (Belal, 2019)
Uncertainty	Product Risk/Performance	Commercial & Content	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018)
	Delivery Risk	Supply chain	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018)
	Product Quality	Commercial & Supply chain	Positive	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018)
	Psychological risk	Marketing, Customer Service, Supply chain & Technology	Positive	• (Ariffin, et al., 2018)
	Social risk	Marketing, Customer Service, Supply chain & Technology	Has No Influence on Purchase intention	• (Ariffin, et al., 2018)

3.8.2. The Reference Models for Research Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this research has captured and combined three different tested modules of Lee & Line (2006), Kennedy & Kundu (2018), and Rita, et al.(2019). (Figures 5, 6 & 7).

- I. Lee & Line (2006) tested module examined the relationship between 5 dimensions of influencing factors (Web site design, Reliability, Responsiveness, Trust & personalization) – separately- with the overall service quality and customer satisfaction, then the relationship of the overall service quality with customer satisfaction and ending with the relationship between the overall service quality and customer satisfaction with the customer purchase intention.

Figure 5: E-service quality model tested by Lee & Line (2006)

e_service quality dimensions

Source: (Lee & Lin, 2006)

- II. While the tested module by Rita, et al.(2019) examined the relationship between 4 dimensions of influencing factors (Web site design, Customer service, Security & Privacy, and fulfillment) – separately- with the overall service quality, then they tested the relationship between the overall service quality with customer satisfaction and customer trust. Finally, they tested the relationship between customer satisfaction with customer purchase intention, word-of-mouth, website re-visit, and the relationship between customer trust with the customer’s intention to purchase and word-of-mouth.

Figure 6: E-service quality model tested by Rita, et al.(2019)

Source: (Rita, et al., 2019)

III. The third module captured is by Kennedy & Kundu (2018) which they have tested the relationship between the shipping fees and chipping lead-time with the purchase decision

Figure 7: E-service quality model for the delivery charge and delivery time tested by Kennedy & Kundu (2018)

Source: (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018)

3.9. Research Gap

As illustrated in this section, “Literature review,” 25 factors that influence online purchase intention have been identified, described, and examined by deferent research using deferent sample characteristics. All researches considered as reference in this literature review were done in Europe and Fare-east “Asia,” except for one research were done in Egypt by Belal (2019).

Belal's study identified the factors influencing consumer satisfaction while shopping online in Egypt, focusing on Egypt's biggest online retailers, "Souq.com and Jumia." Belal (2019) identified six factors only out of the 25 factors illustrated in this section. The studies were done in Europe and Far-east "Asia" were almost aligned in the results of tested factors, while Belal's (2019) analysis, the payment method is a significant factor in consumer satisfaction. Then comes the trust, while security and privacy are not showing significance. The insignificance of security and privacy resulting from Belal's (2019) research is not aligned with other research results (non-Egyptian market), which shows the high significance of security and privacy.

The existing literature review has highlighted several gaps and limitations in the current understanding of factors influencing online purchase intention for the furniture industry in Egypt:

- Lack of Furniture-Specific Studies:

The existing research has not adequately addressed the unique factors influencing online purchase intention in the furniture sector. This represents a significant gap in the literature that the current study aims to fill.

- Demographic Considerations:

This thesis emphasizes the need to consider the demographic differences between the populations studied in the existing literature, as consumer preferences and behaviors may vary across different segments of the Egyptian market

- Inconsistent Findings on E-service Quality Factors:

This thesis suggests that there is a lack of consensus in the literature regarding the relative influence of different e-service quality factors on purchase intention. Further research is needed to clarify these relationships.

- Limited Scope of Egyptian Market Studies:

Belal's (2019) research highlights that previous studies examining the Egyptian e-commerce landscape have focused on a narrow set of factors, such as web design, information quality, order fulfillment, security, trust, and payment methods. This limited scope calls for a more comprehensive investigation of the factors shaping online purchase intentions in the Egyptian furniture industry (Belal, 2019).

These gaps and limitations underscore the need for a more holistic and context-specific examination of the factors influencing online purchase intention in the Egyptian furniture industry. By addressing these research gaps, the current study can provide valuable insights into furniture e-retailers operating in this emerging market.

3.10. Research Problem & Objectives

Egypt's furniture industry is very fragmented and has weak marketing strategies with a limited consumer base for each furniture retailer and manufacturer. Still, most manufacturers and retailers in this industry depend on offline retail, which corresponds to Egyptian consumer behavior while shopping for furniture. With COVID-19, and according to the reports from the

NTRA and Statista, a more significant number of consumers are educated, experienced, and exposed to the idea of doing shopping online in general. However, online shopping of furniture is not typical behavior in the Egyptian market for many reasons that based on subject matter experts of the furniture industry in Egypt:

- **Emphasis on Tangibility and Product Quality:**
 - The subject matter experts in the furniture industry highlighted that Egyptian consumers place a high value on the tactile experience of assessing product quality, including design elements, wood composition, and fabric selection. This emphasis on tangibility presents both opportunities and challenges for the furniture retail sector.
 - The importance of physical interaction with furniture products underscores the need for furniture e-retailers to develop innovative ways to replicate or enhance the in-store experience through features like virtual showrooms and augmented reality (Belal, 2019).
- **Demand for Transparent Pricing and Value-for-Money:**
 - Belal's (2019) study indicates a growing demand among Egyptian consumers for transparent pricing structures that accurately reflect the quality of the products, suggesting a sophisticated consumer base that prioritizes value-for-money propositions.
 - This trend highlights the need for furniture retailers, both online and offline, to clearly communicate the rationale behind their pricing strategies and to offer competitive yet fair pricing that aligns with the perceived value of their products.
- **Preference for Customized Solutions and Expert Consultation:**
 - The theses suggest that the Egyptian furniture market demonstrates a preference for customized solutions, which often necessitates the involvement of industry experts in person.
 - This trend underscores the importance of maintaining a balance between digital innovation and traditional consultation methods, as consumers may still value the personalized guidance and expertise provided by in-store design consultants.
- **Cautious Approach and Reliance on Word-of-Mouth:**
 - This research highlights a prevailing sentiment among Egyptian consumers of caution when engaging in furniture purchases, particularly concerning aspects such as design fidelity, product, and material quality, adherence to delivery schedules, warranty terms, and financial risk mitigation.
 - Consequently, word-of-mouth recommendations play a crucial role in expanding the consumer base for furniture retailers and manufacturers, as consumers seek to mitigate perceived risks through the experiences and endorsements of their peers (Belal, 2019).
- **Restrictive Photography Policies and Intellectual Property Concerns:**

- The subject matter experts in the furniture industry note that most furniture retailers and manufacturers have implemented policies restricting photography within their showrooms, rooted in the belief that it safeguards their intellectual property from unauthorized replication.
- The industry experts suggests that such measures may encourage direct consumer engagement with their exclusive designs in physical retail environments, potentially limiting the ability of e-commerce platforms to effectively showcase and market these products.
- Informal Sector and Tax Compliance Concerns:
 - The industry experts highlight that a significant portion of the furniture industry, including both retailers and manufacturers, operates within the informal sector, leading to concerns regarding tax compliance.
 - There is a perception among these businesses that transitioning to online platforms may increase their visibility to regulatory bodies, potentially leading to enhanced scrutiny of their tax obligations and licensing requirements.

The illustrated reasons by subject matter experts are subjectively reflecting a narrow vision that is influenced by the following:

- Limited Experience and Knowledge of Furniture Retailers and Manufacturers:

The limited experience and lack of formal education in e-commerce and global understanding of Egyptian consumer behavior among furniture retailers and manufacturers may contribute to gaps in addressing unfulfilled needs and influencing factors on purchase intention, decision, and satisfaction.

- Resistance to Digital Transformation:

Despite the high cost of running offline furniture businesses, many retailers and manufacturers are uncomfortable with the decision to undergo digital transformation, as e-commerce may be perceived as less familiar and more complex compared to traditional operations.

- Growing Influence of E-commerce and Online Furniture Platforms:

The web search results indicate that Egyptian consumers are increasingly exposed to the Internet and the emergence of various online furniture retailers, which may be replicating successful business models from international markets. This trend underscores the need to understand how these new e-commerce players are shaping consumer preferences and behaviors in the furniture industry.

- Evolving Trends in the Egyptian Furniture Industry:

The web search results reveal several emerging trends in the Egyptian furniture industry, including the rise of e-commerce, the adoption of technologies like virtual reality and augmented reality, the focus on sustainable materials and manufacturing, the integration of smart features in furniture, and the optimization of supply chain operations.

- Changing Consumer Preferences and Behaviors:

The web search results highlight that the Egyptian furniture market is being shaped by factors such as the growing middle class with increased disposable income, the shift towards online shopping for furniture, the demand for personalized and sustainable products, and the competition from cheap imports, which is driving local manufacturers to improve quality and efficiency.

- Cultural and Social Significance of Furniture in Egypt:

The web search results emphasize the cultural, economic, and social importance of furniture in Egypt, where it serves as a representation of the country's rich history of craftsmanship, a driver of economic activity, and a means of creating hospitable living spaces and supporting the hospitality industry.

The research's main objective here is to determine which e-service quality factors influence Egyptian consumers' purchase intention when buying furniture from an online platform. However, there are secondary objectives as follows:

- To investigate Homzmart's e-service quality performance
- To investigate the significance "if any" of e-service quality dimensions to achieve overall service quality and consumer satisfaction
- to investigate which "if any" of the service quality dimensions are more significant in influencing purchase intention.

3.11. Major Research Question & Minor Research Questions

The fragmentation of the furniture market, lacking the proper marketing strategies, inefficiency in cost and production, culture and taste changes, and last but not least, the consumers' behavior towards digital transformation. These are the significant current challenges the furniture industry faces; thus, players in this industry should consider e-commerce as a future retail channel. e-retail is an entirely different game than offline retail since there is no face-to-face interaction between the seller and buyer, which is considered one of the essential tactics that buyers are considering when doing business.

By considering the research objectives, here is the major question for this research to answer:

- I. What are the factors of e-service quality that influencing the consumer's online purchase intention of furniture in Egypt?
- II. By considering customer satisfaction and overall service quality as mediator variables, which one of these mediator variables significantly influences consumers' online purchase intention of furniture in Egypt?

Minor questions:

- I. What is the significance influence of the e-service quality dimensions on the furniture purchase intention of Egyptian consumers when buying from an online platform?

- II. As a furniture manufacturer or retailer, by knowing the online influencing factors on furniture purchase intention of the Egyptian consumer, should they consider having their online platforms or partnering with the current platforms for household/retail?

4. The Research Methodology

The literature review section discussed the different models and dimensions of the factors of e-service quality. The research objective is to identify and investigate the e-service quality dimensions and understand how these e-service quality dimensions could contribute to the purchase intention of furniture in Egypt.

This section aims to set an operational strategy to answer the research objectives via proper statistical analysis. It presents the following sub-sections:

- 4.1. [Research Philosophy](#)
- 4.2. [Research Approach](#)
- 4.3. [Research Design](#)
- 4.4. [Unit Of Analysis](#)
- 4.5. [Data Collection: Questionnaire And Constructs](#)
- 4.6. [Time Horizon](#)
- 4.7. [Population & Sample](#)
- 4.8. [Research Framework](#)

4.1. Research Philosophy

The researcher aims to examine the influence of the e-service quality factors (Website design, Online Service, and Convenience) on online purchase intentions. The researcher adopted the positivism philosophy for this research. This selection because the researcher will test a general theory -that has been tested before within different scopes/industries- for a specific scope (furniture industry, Egypt, and Homzmart). This philosophy describes the phenomena that other researchers have validated, and this research aims to confirm if this current phenomenon is valid to its scope or not.

4.2. Research Approach

There are two common approaches for any research, deductive and inductive.

The deductive approach gets adopted when the researcher is studying a general phenomenon/observation to a specific scope. It requires the validity of the results of the general theory or observation. Here the researcher collects data to examine the hypothesis related to the general theory.

The inductive approach gets adopted when the researcher is studying a specific phenomenon/observation to be generalized. Using this approach, the researcher collects data that will be used to explore a phenomenon and then define the model/theory. It generates a general theory based on a specific observation; this is why the conclusion may be right or wrong.

The adopted approach for this research is the deductive approach. The researcher works from general theory to a specific scope. The research will examine the relationship between the e-service quality factors (Website design, Online Service, and Convenience) and the online purchase intention of furniture in Egypt, a case study of Homzmart.com.

4.3. Research Design

This research adopted the deductive approach where the researcher will use the quantitative methodology to examine the statistical relationship between the e-service quality factors with the online purchase intention of furniture in Egypt, a case study of Homzmart.com. The most communal module to measure e-service quality is the SERVQUAL model and it is still popular and currently used in many studies (Rita, et al., 2019). The conceptual model design of this research is considering the e-service quality factors (illustrated in section 2.7.1) to be examined using the SERVQUAL model. Here the researcher took three references of tested modules of Rita, et al. (2019), Lee & Lin (2006), and Kennedy & Kundu (2018) (illustrated in section 2.7.2).

The conclusion from section 2.7, all literature reviews presented showed the significance of the captured e-service quality factors on online purchase intention. This research aims to investigate the same modules for a specific scope (Furniture, Egypt, Homzmart.com) by using a quantitative design (questionnaire method).

4.4. Unit of Analysis

The researcher will collect the primary data throughout the questionnaire method (quantitative design). The participants in this questioner are Homzmart's customers in Egypt who purchased furniture products. The unit of analysis in this research represented customers of Homzmart in Egypt.

4.5. Data collection: questionnaire and construction

The data will be collected through a questionnaire (quantitative design). The questions have been captured from three modules of Rita, et al. (2019), Lee & Lin (2006), Van Der Merwe (2010), and Kennedy & Kundu (2018). Subject matter experts will validate the questioner in e-retail in general and e-retail for furniture in specific.

It will be distributed electronically to the targeted population, and the collection of the data will be done electronically and with no human interference.

Table 6: The questionnaire for the quantitative analysis

Dimension	Factors	Items	Answers	Restrictions
General Questions	Demographics	DE1. Your Gender	Male or Female	One Answer
	Demographics	DE1. Your Age Range	20-24 , 25-29, 30-34, 35-39, 40-44, 45+	One Answer

General access

	Demographics	DE1. Governate	List of Governates	One Answer
	Demographics	DE1. Living City	List of Cities	One Answer
	Demographics	DE1. Educational Level	List of educational levels	One Answer
	Demographics	DE1. Profession	Open Field	Must to be answered
	Demographics	DE1. Did you experience online shopping for any product or service before?	Yes or No	One Answer
	Demographics	DE1. Please select from the below list the online platforms that you did purchase from them?*	List of Online Platforms	Multiple selections allowed
	Demographics	DE1. Did you purchase any furniture products from Homzmart before?	Yes or No	One Answer
Website Design	Website Aesthetics	WA1. This site shows creativity	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		WA2. The website displays a visually pleasing design.		
		WA3. This site offers good illustrations of the products		
		WA4. The design is appropriate for this type of site		
	Purchase Process	PP1. The website has no difficulties with making a payment online	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		PP2. The purchasing process was not difficult.		
		PP3. It is easier to use the website to complete my purchase with the company than to use a telephone or mail or texting via social media the company's representative.		
	Website Convenience	WC1. The website displays a visually pleasing easy to read the content.	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		WC2. The text on the website is easy to read.		
		WC3. The website labels are easy to understand.		
		WC4. The organization and layout of this site makes it easier to search for information		
	Website Personalization	WP1. The website has interactive features, which help me accomplish my shopping	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree	One Answer
		WP2. I can interact with the website in order to get information tailored to my specific needs.		

General access

			5=Strongly Agree	
	System Availability	SA1. When I use the website, there is very little waiting time between my actions and the website's response.	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		SA2. The website loads quickly.		
Online Service	Information Quality	IQ1. The information on the website is pretty much what I need to carry out my shopping	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		IQ2. The website adequately meets my information needs.		
	Communication & Interaction	SL1. Homzmart provides a telephone number for support	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		SL2. Homzmart has customer service representatives available online.		
		SL3. Homzmart offers the ability to speak to a live person if there is a problem.		
		SL4. Homzmart offers multiple communication means for convenience		
		SL5. Customer service shows adequate understanding of the product and the provided service		
	SL6. Customer service interaction with me is appropriate with high quality			
	Responsiveness	RS1. The customer service agents are responding on time to my inquiries	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		RS2. The customer service responsiveness when I have a problem with the order, they respond very fast		
	Consistency	CO1. Every time I purchase from Homzmart, I receive the expected product quality	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		CO2. Every time I purchase from Homzmart, I receive the expected delivery service quality		
		CO3. Every time I purchase from Homzmart, I receive the proper customer service support		
CO4. The information on the site is always available				
CO5. The information on the site is consistent				

General access

Convenience	Better Prices	PO1. The website offers discounts or free shipping.	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		PO2. The website has low prices.		
		PO3. The website has lower prices than offline stores.		
	Broader Selection	PS1. All my shopping with Homzmart can be completed via the website	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		PS2. This website has a good selection.		
		PS3. The site has a wide variety of products that interest me.		
	Delivery Time	TD1. The product is delivered by the time promised by Homzmart	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		TD2. Homzmart makes items available for delivery within a suitable time frame.		
		TD3. Homzmart quickly delivers what I order.		
	Time-Saving	TS1. It is easy to navigate and to find what I am looking for on this site quickly	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		TS2. Homzmart shopping features helped me to find the product I look for quickly		
		TS3. Homzmart check-out page makes my purchase actions easy and quick		
	Delivery Charge	DC1. The shipping cost is clear and easy to be calculated	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		DC2. The shipping cost is fair when compared to others		
		DC3. The shipping cost could prevent me not to proceed with the purchase when compared to the product price		
	Overall e-Service Quality	SQ1. Overall. my purchase experience with Homzmart is excellent	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	One Answer
		SQ2. The overall quality of the service provided by Homzmart is excellent		
		SQ3. My overall feelings toward Homzmart are very satisfied		
Customer Satisfaction	S1. I am satisfied with Homzmart as the online shop for Furniture	1=Strongly Disagree 2=Disagree 3=Natural	One Answer	
	S2. Homzmart is getting close to the ideal online retailer.			

	S3. Homzmart always meets my needs.	4=Agree	
	S4. I strongly recommend Homzmart for family & friends	5=Strongly Agree	
Repurchase Intention	RI1. I will make more purchases through Homzmart in the future.	1=Strongly Disagree	One Answer
	RI2. Homzmart is my first online platform first choice for future purchase	2=Disagree 3=Natural 4=Agree 5=Strongly Agree	

Source: (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018) (Lee & Lin, 2006) (Rita, et al., 2019) (Van Der Merwe, 2010)

4.6. Time Horizon

Homzmart is still at the ramp-up phase, and there are developmental actions are regularly introduced in terms of overall customer experience. This is considered as a factor that might influence the accuracy of the answers during the time horizon. Accordingly, this research will be adopting the time horizon type of cross-sectional data where the e-service quality factors will be tested in a one- and specific-time horizon.

4.7. Population & Sample

4.7.1. The population

This research aims to examine the impact of e-service quality factors on the online purchase intention of furniture in Egypt. Therefore, the population of this research is Homzmart’s customers who purchased a furniture product at least once. The size of this population is almost fifty thousand consumers.

4.7.2. The sample size

In order to validate the hypotheses of this research, the researcher adopted the quantitative approach using questioner. By considering the size of the targeted population (Five thousand consumers) and adopting a confidence level of 95% and margin of error at 5%, accordingly the sample size is 357participants.

4.8. Research Framework

According to what has been explained in section 3.3, “The research design,” the researcher combined the factors of the three modules of Lee & Line (2006), Kennedy & Kundu (2018), and Rita, et al.(2019). Then the researcher selected the more critical factors for Homzmart “as the case of this study” to test their relationship with the overall service quality from a side and the relationship of these factors on customer satisfaction from another side. Since purchase intention could be influenced by previous purchase experience or website surfing/word-of-mouth experience, the researcher had to test “separately” the relationship of the e-service quality factors on overall service quality and customer satisfaction.

Here, the researcher uses the same approach as Lee & Line (2006) to assess the relationship and the influencing level of each factor separately on overall service quality and customer satisfaction. Then, testing the relationship of overall customer satisfaction with customer

satisfaction and finally testing the relationship of both (the overall service quality and customer satisfaction) with the purchase intention.

Figure 8: The Research Model

4.8.1. Operationalization

- *Selection of the Influencing Factors on online purchase intention*

Three criteria developed, where the author of this research will decide the factors that will be selected and the model that will be examined (See Table 6):

- I. Any influencing factor was not tested before for online shopping of furniture in Egypt to be selected

- II. All influencing factors under consumer attitude (consumer perceived risk) should be excluded because creating positive word of mouth could positively influence consumer attitude, which needs to be studied in another research as intermediate variables. These factors were also tested recently in three different papers with three different testing methodologies, and the results are consistent.
- III. The priority to Homzmart – ambiguous area to Homzmart to be selected

Table 7: Subjective analysis for influencing factors illustrated in the literature review for selection decision and modeling for this research (C is referring to Criteria)

Dimensions	Influencing Factors	C1	C 2	C 3	Source	Selection Priority
Online Service	Responsiveness	√	√	√	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	Communication & Interaction	√	√	√	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	Consistency	√	√	√	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	Product Information Quality	√	√	√	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
Convenience	Better Prices	√	√	√	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	Time-Saving	√	√	√	• (Chen, et al., 2016) (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	Broader Selection	√	√	√	• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	Delivery Charge	√	√	√	• (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018)	Selected
	Delivery Time	√	√	√	• (Kennedy & Kundu, 2018) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
Visual	Brand	√	√		• (Mazurova, 2017)	Not Selected
	Color	√	√		• (Mazurova, 2017)	Not Selected
	Product position on the website	√	√		• (Mazurova, 2017)	Not Selected
Website design	Website Aesthetics	√	√	√	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	Purchase Process	√	√	√	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	Website Convenience	√	√	√	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	Website Personalization	√	√	√	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected
	System Availability	√	√	√	• (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Selected

Trust & Risk	Trust	√			• (Chen, et al., 2016) (Belal, 2019)	Not Selected
	Privacy Risk	√			• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018) (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Not Selected
	Financial Security	√			• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018) (Belal, 2019) • (Rita, et al., 2019)	Not Selected
Uncertainty	Product Risk/Performance	√			• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018)	Not Selected
	Delivery Risk	√			• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018)	Not Selected
	Product Quality	√			• (Chen, et al., 2016) • (Ariffin, et al., 2018)	Not Selected
	Psychological risk	√			• (Ariffin, et al., 2018)	Not Selected
	Social risk	√			• (Ariffin, et al., 2018)	Not Selected

- *Research variables*

The research variables were defined and adopted accordingly to study the relationship between the consumer's online purchase intention and the e-service quality factors. The research variables are segmented as follows:

- The Independent Variable:

The e-service quality factors with the three selected dimensions:

- Online Services
- Convenience
- Website Design

- The Mediator Variables:

- The overall service quality
- Customer satisfaction

- The Dependent Variable:

- The purchase intention is the dependent variable when the consumer interacts with Homzmart.com in the furniture industry in Egypt

4.8.2. The Research Hypothesis

H1 - The online service has a statistically significant relationship with overall service quality

H2 - The online service has a statistically significant relationship with consumer satisfaction

H3 - Convenience has a statistically significant relationship with overall service quality

H4 - Convenience has a statistically significant relationship with consumer satisfaction

H5 - The website design has a statistically significant relationship with overall service quality

H6 - The website design has a statistically significant relationship with consumer satisfaction

H7 - The overall service quality has a statistically significant relationship with consumer satisfaction

H8 - The overall service quality has a statistically significant relationship with online purchase intention

H9 - Consumer satisfaction has a statistically significant relationship with online purchase intention

4.8.3. Research Limitation

This research to identify, examine and understand the factors influencing the online purchase intention of the Egyptian consumer when buying furniture from an online retailer.

The researcher conducted the literature review using the list of relevant keywords, and the resources considered and captured in this research were free of charge.

1. The online influencing factors on online purchase intention are limited to what has been captured from the resources captured in the literature review and till the year 2020
2. The scope is the Furniture industry in Egypt and The Egyptian Consumer.
3. Taking Homzmart as the case for this study
4. This research is based on social science. Accordingly, future researchers should consider the changes in consumer behavior, business environment, digital maturity, and any other factors that may influence changes or additions in the captured online influencing factors on furniture purchase intention Egypt.

5. Research Ethics

There are four ethical principles - from the perspective of the participants in this research, the scientific community, and society - are considered to conduct this research:

- Weighing risks against benefits
- Acting responsibly and with integrity
- Seeking justice
- Respecting people's rights and dignity

This section flows as below:

5.1 [The research scope](#)

5.2 [Selection of the influencing factors](#)

5.3 [Selection of the population](#)

5.4 [Survey questions validation and data gathering](#)

5.5 [Business and Personal information confidentiality](#)

5.1. The research scope

This study focuses on identifying the influencing factors on consumer intention to buy furniture from online platforms in Egypt. The research scope is defined by three principal components:

- The study focuses on the furniture business, analyzing the distinct characteristics and issues related to the sale and purchase of furniture via digital channels. This industry-specific emphasis facilitates a more profound comprehension of the elements that affect online furniture acquisitions specifically.
- The study concentrates on online platforms as the primary channel for furniture purchases. In this regard, Homzmart is chosen as a case study, exemplifying an e-commerce platform in the Egyptian furniture sector. This emphasis on Homzmart for a comprehensive analysis of the elements affecting consumer intentions in a particular online furniture retail context.
- The research focuses on internet platforms as the principal medium for furniture acquisitions. In this regard, Homzmart is chosen as a case study, exemplifying an e-commerce platform in the Egyptian furniture sector. This emphasis on Homzmart for a comprehensive analysis of the elements affecting consumer intentions in a particular online furniture retail context.

This research seeks to delineate certain boundaries to offer precise insights into the elements affecting consumer desire to purchase furniture online in Egypt, while ensuring a focused and controllable scope of inquiry.

5.2. Identification of the influencing factors

This study aimed to investigate the correlation between the online service quality factors outlined in the research hypothesis and overall service quality and customer satisfaction, as well as the association of overall service quality with customer satisfaction, culminating in the relationship between overall service quality, customer satisfaction, and online purchase intention. This examination is limited to the factors selected by Homzmart's management that are interesting for them to understand and measure. Accordingly, this research is limited to selected factors and not all factors identified in the literature review. It is worth mentioning that other factors could not be identified in the literature review, so other researchers should consider this for future research on this topic.

5.3. Selection of the population

The study focuses on Homzmart as the case study. Accordingly, the population will be selected from Homzmart customer base, whether they bought from Homzmart before or just registered on its website, and limited customers located in Greater Cairo and Alexandria.

5.4. Survey questions validation and data gathering

Subject matter experts will validate the survey questions gathered from the research done by Rita, et al. (2019) before sharing the survey with the selected population. The subject matter

experts' selection will consider three criteria, Experts in Online shopping, Experts in the furniture industry, and digital Marketers.

When the survey is published, the researcher will offer the survey participants a discount voucher from Homzmart granted by Homzmart to their customers. The value of this voucher with equal value to all despite their answers. This voucher will be granted on the spot when the participant's answers get submitted.

5.5. Business and Personal information confidentiality

The researcher has obtained Homzmart's management approval to conduct this research using Homzmart data and its business insights to be the case considered in this study. Any business information, data, figures that are considered confidential by Homzmart Management are not declared; however, the approved insights "only" are illustrated in a way not declaring the exact figures.

The survey will be conducted digitally on an anomalous basis, so no personal information of the survey participants is captured. Only participants' demographics are collected as part of the survey answers and gathered in a scientific way to serve this study's scientific purposes.

5.6. Execution of the survey

The Homzmart team executed the survey digitally using Google Forms, utilizing a questionnaire developed by the researcher (see to Appendix 11.1). The survey questionnaire was available in both Arabic and English to accommodate linguistic preferences. The primary structure of the questions was multiple-choice or selection boxes, however a handful required concise written solutions. Participants were afforded the option to respond in either English or Arabic.

The sampling frame consisted of 5,000 consumer contacts sourced from Homzmart's customer database. The survey was disseminated through a multi-channel approach, utilizing both email and WhatsApp to deliver the survey link. The research team utilized opportunistic sampling by inviting consumers at Homzmart's physical location to participate in the study.

6. Analytical Techniques and Statistical Assessments

This section outlines the comprehensive methodology for data analysis employed in this study regarding the factors influencing customer intent to purchase furniture from online platforms in Egypt, with a specific focus on Homzmart.com. The analytical method involves a thorough examination of the relationships among e-service quality metrics, overall service quality, customer happiness, and purchase intention in the context of online furniture retail.

The data analysis process has three fundamental steps, each employing specific statistical techniques to achieve the research goals:

1. **Data Preparation:** This initial process involves dataset cleansing, managing missing values, and structuring the data for analysis. It ensures the integrity and reliability of the subsequent statistical procedures.
2. **Descriptive Statistics:** Employing measures of central tendency and variability to provide a succinct overview of sample characteristics and response patterns.

3. Reliability and Validity Evaluation: Cronbach's alpha and factor analysis will be utilized to analyze the internal consistency and construct validity of our measurement scales.
4. Inferential Statistics: A range of statistical tests, including as correlation analysis, multiple regression, and structural equation modeling, will be employed to assess our hypotheses and examine the relationships among variables.
5. Mediation and Moderation Analysis: These advanced approaches will clarify the complex connections among our variables of interest.

This comprehensive analytical approach seeks to provide a detailed understanding of the factors influencing online furniture purchasing intentions in Egypt. This study will augment the scholarly literature on e-commerce in emerging markets and offer practical insights for online furniture retailers in Egypt..

This section flows as below:

- [6.1. Data Preparation](#)
- [6.2. Descriptive Statistics](#)
- [6.3. Reliability Analysis](#)
- [6.4. Exploratory Factor Analysis \(EFA\)](#)
- [6.5. Confirmatory Factor Analysis \(CFA\)](#)
- [6.6. Correlation Analysis](#)
- [6.7. Multiple Regression Analysis](#)
- [6.8. Mediation Analysis](#)
- [6.9. Moderation Analysis](#)
- [6.10. Structural Equation Modeling \(SEM\)](#)
- [6.11. Analysis of Variance \(ANOVA\)](#)
- [6.12. Non-parametric Tests](#)
- [6.13. Statistical Software](#)
- [6.14. Significance Level](#)
- [6.15. Effect Size Calculation](#)

6.1. Data Preparation

6.1.1. Data Cleaning

The data cleaning process is an essential preliminary step in guaranteeing the quality and integrity of our dataset. This method entails a comprehensive review and remediation of the raw data to detect and rectify any flaws that may affect the precision of our analysis. This study emphasizes three fundamental features of data cleaning:

1. Initially, systematically eliminating incomplete or invalid responses from our dataset. This phase is vital for preserving the integrity of our findings, since it removes items that are deficient in critical information or contain logically inconsistent responses.
2. Secondly, meticulously identify and address outliers. Outliers, defined as data points that markedly diverge from other observations, might disproportionately affect our statistical analysis. Utilizing statistical methodologies and specialized understanding of the

Egyptian furniture e-commerce sector to identify authentic outliers and ascertain the most suitable treatment approach.

3. Finally, rectify any absent data with suitable imputation methods. Improperly managed missing data might result in biased outcomes and diminished statistical power. Meticulously assess the pattern of missingness in our dataset and implement appropriate imputation techniques that maintain the statistical integrity of our data while optimizing the utilization of existing information.

The objective of rigorously executing these data cleaning techniques is to establish a stable and dependable dataset that will underpin our forthcoming analysis of consumer intents to purchase furniture from online platforms in Egypt, particularly Homzmart.com.

6.1.2. Data Coding

The data coding process is a crucial phase in the preparation of acquired data for analysis. This process entails converting raw data into a format appropriate for statistical analysis, guaranteeing consistency and precision across the dataset. This step will have two main tasks:

1. Initially, open-ended responses will be methodically coded. This procedure entails meticulously analyzing the qualitative data supplied by respondents and allocating suitable numerical or categorical classifications. These codes will encapsulate the core of the responses while facilitating quantitative analysis. This stage is crucial for comprehending nuanced consumer viewpoints regarding online furniture acquisition in Egypt.
2. Secondly, reverse-scored objects will undergo recording. Certain questionnaire items may have been deliberately articulated in a reverse manner to mitigate response bias. The objects will be recognized and recorded to provide uniform scaling of all variables. The recording process is crucial for preserving data integrity and facilitating proper result interpretation inside the Egyptian e-commerce furniture sector.

Through these coding techniques, the raw data will be converted into a structured manner, enabling rigorous statistical analysis and ensuring the validity of subsequent conclusions concerning consumer intents to purchase furniture from online platforms like Homzmart.com.

6.1.3. Data Transformation

The data transformation phase is an essential step in preparing the dataset for thorough analysis. This phase entails the manipulation of cleaned and coded data to generate significant variables and confirm the fulfillment of statistical assumptions. This phase will involve two principal tasks:

1. Composite scores for multi-item scales will be calculated initially. This approach entails amalgamating individual item responses into composite measures that signify broader constructions pertinent to online furniture shopping behavior in Egypt. These composite ratings will offer a more comprehensive and dependable assessment of essential characteristics, including e-service quality dimensions and customer happiness.

2. Secondly, essential variable transformations will be executed to rectify any breaches of statistical assumptions. If data for certain variables demonstrate considerable skewness, suitable transformations (e.g., logarithmic transformation) will be utilized. These modifications are crucial for maintaining the integrity of subsequent statistical studies and the precision of conclusions concerning customer intents to acquire furniture from online platforms such as Homzmart.com.

Employing the aforementioned transformation processes, the dataset will be refined for analysis, facilitating a more detailed and precise investigation of the elements affecting online furniture purchasing behavior in the Egyptian market.

6.2. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics are essential for delivering a thorough summary of the gathered data, elucidating the attributes of the sample and the distribution of responses. This phase of analysis has numerous essential elements that will be employed to succinctly summarize and present the findings.

1. Measures of central tendency, comprising the mean, median, and mode, will be computed to ascertain the typical or average responses about numerous factors associated with online furniture shopping behavior in Egypt. These measures will elucidate the fundamental values inside the dataset.
2. Measures of dispersion, including standard deviation and range, will be calculated to supplement the central tendency measures. These statistics will provide insights into the heterogeneity and dispersion of the data, emphasizing the range of replies among Egyptian consumers concerning their online furniture shopping experiences and goals.
3. Frequency distributions and percentages will be produced to demonstrate the proportion of responses within various categories or value ranges. This analysis will be essential in comprehending the distribution of demographic traits and categorical factors associated with e-commerce preferences.
4. Visual representations, such as histograms, bar charts, and pie charts, will be generated to illustrate the data graphically. These visualizations will provide an easy and accessible method for interpreting the patterns and trends within the dataset, enhancing comprehension of the factors affecting customer intents to purchase furniture from online platforms such as Homzmart.com.

These descriptive statistical techniques will establish a thorough initial grasp of the dataset, providing a foundation for more complex analysis in the later stages of the project.

6.3. Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis is an essential phase in evaluating the consistency and stability of the measuring devices employed in this investigation. This analytical phase concentrates on assessing the reliability of multi-item scales used to gauge essential constructs associated with online furniture shopping behavior in Egypt. Three principal strategies will be employed to guarantee the integrity of the measurements:

1. Cronbach's alpha will be computed to evaluate the internal consistency of multi-item scales. This commonly employed reliability coefficient indicates the extent to which the items on a scale assess the same underlying construct. Evaluating the dependability of scales that measure e-service quality characteristics, customer happiness, and purchase intents is particularly crucial in the context of online furniture retail.
2. Item-total correlations will be analyzed to assess the relationship between individual items and the overall scale score. This analysis aids in identifying items that may lack consistency with the remainder of the scale, hence potentially enhancing the overall dependability of the measures.
3. Inter-item correlations will be examined to evaluate the links among individual items within a scale. This analysis offers insights into the scale's coherence and assists in identifying any redundant or inconsistent elements.

The reliability analyses will demonstrate the integrity and consistency of the measurement scales, providing a robust foundation for subsequent analyses of factors impacting consumer intentions to purchase furniture from online platforms such as Homzmart.com in the Egyptian market.

6.4. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is an essential analytical method for investigating the underlying structure of the measurement scales utilized in this investigation. This approach is especially significant for comprehending the complexity of constructs associated with online furniture shopping behavior in the Egyptian market. The EFA procedure will include several essential stages:

1. The dimensionality of measurement scales will be evaluated to determine the underlying components that elucidate the relationships among observed variables. This stage is crucial for validating the conceptual framework and confirming that the measured constructs appropriately reflect the theoretical notions.
2. Either Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) will be utilized as the extraction approach, contingent upon the data's specific properties and the study aims. These strategies will assist in determining the principal factors elucidating the variance in the observed variables.
3. Rotation techniques, such as Varimax or Oblimin, will be utilized according to the anticipated correlations among components. This process facilitates the simplification of the factor structure and enhances its interpretability, yielding clearer insights into the dimensions of e-service quality and other pertinent constructs within the context of Homzmart.com and analogous platforms.
4. Factor retention decisions will be determined by several criteria, including eigenvalues exceeding 1, study of the scree plot, and parallel analysis. These criteria guarantee that only relevant and statistically significant factors are preserved for subsequent investigation.

This rigorous EFA procedure will elucidate the underlying structure of the data, establishing a robust foundation for comprehending the principal characteristics that affect customer intents to purchase furniture from online platforms in Egypt.

6.5. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is essential for validating the measurement model established using exploratory factor analysis. This sophisticated statistical method is utilized to meticulously evaluate the proposed framework of latent variables associated with online furniture shopping behavior in the Egyptian market. The CFA process includes several essential elements:

1. The measurement model will be evaluated to ascertain the links between observed variables and their corresponding latent constructs. This stage is crucial for verifying that the theoretical framework appropriately reflects the actual data gathered from users of online furniture marketplaces such as Homzmart.com.
2. Model fit will be evaluated utilizing various indices, such as the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). These indices enable a thorough assessment of the proposed model's fit to the observed data, providing insights on the measurement structure's validity.
3. Factor loadings will be analyzed to assess the strength of the link between each observed variable and its respective latent construct. Furthermore, modification indices will be examined to pinpoint feasible enhancements to the model fit, guaranteeing that the final measurement model precisely reflects the intricacies of e-service quality and other pertinent structures within the realm of online furniture shopping in Egypt.

This rigorous CFA approach will demonstrate the validity of the measurement model, providing a robust framework for subsequent evaluations of the determinants impacting consumer intentions to purchase furniture from online platforms in the Egyptian market.

6.6. Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is a crucial step in investigating the links between factors pertinent to online furniture purchasing behavior in the Egyptian market. This analytical method elucidates the intensity and orientation of relationships among principal conceptions. The correlation analysis will employ diverse methodologies to address distinct sorts of variables:

1. Pearson's correlation coefficient will be utilized to evaluate the linear associations between continuous variables. This measure will assess the degree and direction of connections among characteristics such as e-service quality aspects, customer satisfaction, and purchase intents for platforms like Homzmart.com.
2. Spearman's rank correlation will be employed for ordinal variables. This non-parametric metric is especially advantageous for assessing correlations between variables that lack a normal distribution or are quantified on an ordinal scale, such as consumer evaluations or preference hierarchies.

3. Point-biserial correlation will be utilized to analyze relationships between pairs of dichotomous and continuous variables. This approach is helpful in elucidating the relationship between binary variables (e.g., first-time versus repeat consumers) and continuous metrics of customer behavior or sentiments within the online furniture retail sector.

This correlation analysis will clarify the interrelationships among factors affecting consumer intentions to purchase furniture online in Egypt, establishing a basis for more sophisticated statistical methods and insights into the dynamics of the e-commerce furniture market.

6.7. Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis serves as a pivotal statistical technique in this study, aimed at unraveling the complex relationships between various factors influencing consumer purchase intentions in the online furniture market of Egypt. This sophisticated analytical approach allows for a comprehensive examination of how multiple independent variables simultaneously impact the dependent variable of interest.

The analysis will begin by assessing the impact of multiple independent variables on the dependent variable, purchase intention. This step is crucial in understanding how various aspects of e-service quality, customer satisfaction, and other relevant factors collectively influence consumers' intentions to purchase furniture from online platforms like Homzmart.com.

Prior to conducting the regression analysis, key assumptions will be rigorously checked to ensure the validity of the results. These include linearity, normality, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity. This thorough examination of assumptions is essential for producing reliable and meaningful insights into the Egyptian e-commerce furniture market.

Stepwise regression will be employed to identify the most significant predictors of purchase intention. This method allows for a systematic approach to variable selection, highlighting the factors that have the strongest influence on consumers' decisions to buy furniture online in Egypt.

Additionally, hierarchical regression will be utilized to test theoretical models. This approach enables the examination of how different sets of variables contribute to explaining the variance in purchase intention, providing insights into the relative importance of various factors in the context of online furniture retail.

Through this comprehensive multiple regression analysis, a nuanced understanding of the factors driving consumer purchase intentions in the Egyptian online furniture market will be developed, offering valuable insights for both academic research and industry practitioners.

6.8. Mediation Analysis

Mediation analysis acts as a crucial statistical tool in this study, aimed at identifying the underlying processes via which numerous factors influence customer intention to purchase furniture from online platforms in Egypt. This comprehensive analytical technique enables for a greater understanding of the complicated relationships between variables in the context of e-commerce furniture retail.

The analysis will apply different methodologies to guarantee a full investigation of potential mediating effects:

1. Baron and Kenny's four-step methodology will be applied as a basic strategy to develop mediation. This traditional method offers a structured framework for discovering and examining mediating interactions among variables associated with online furniture purchasing behavior.
2. The Sobel test will be performed to evaluate the statistical significance of the mediation effects. This test provides a quantitative assessment of the significance of the indirect impact, yielding essential insights into the robustness of the mediating relationships within the Egyptian online furniture industry.
3. Furthermore, the bootstrap technique will be utilized to compute confidence intervals for indirect effects. This contemporary method provides a strong means to assess the durability and dependability of mediation effects, especially pertinent in the realm of intricate e-commerce activities.

This mediation research seeks to clarify the complex relationships between elements, including e-service quality characteristics and customer happiness, and their impact on consumer intents to purchase furniture from online platforms such as Homzmart.com in Egypt. This investigation will yield significant insights for both theoretical comprehension and practical implementation in the swiftly changing domain of online furniture shopping.

6.9. Moderation Analysis

Moderation analysis is essential for comprehending the intricate interactions between variables that affect customer intentions to acquire furniture from online platforms in Egypt. This analytical method seeks to discover and analyze the conditions in which the relationship between predictor factors and the outcome variable (purchase intention) may fluctuate in strength or direction.

The investigation will employ two principal methodologies to comprehensively examine potential moderating effects:

1. Interaction terms will be incorporated into regression models to examine moderation effects. This methodology facilitates the analysis of how the interplay between essential variables, such as e-service quality dimensions and purchase intention, may be affected by additional factors pertinent to the Egyptian online furniture industry.
2. For discovered significant interactions, a simple slopes analysis will be performed. This technique offers a more nuanced comprehension of the moderating effect, demonstrating how the link between variables varies at different degrees of the moderator.

This thorough moderation analysis will provide insights into the intricate dynamics influencing consumer behavior in the realm of online furniture shopping in Egypt. These findings will

enhance the understanding of the conditions that most significantly affect purchase intentions on platforms such as Homzmart.com.

6.10. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a robust analytical method utilized in this study, providing an extensive framework for testing and evaluating the theoretical model of consumer intent to purchase furniture from online platforms in Egypt. This advanced statistical technique enables the concurrent analysis of many correlations between observed and latent variables, offering a comprehensive perspective on the factors affecting online furniture purchasing behavior.

The SEM study will include several essential elements:

1. The comprehensive theoretical model will be evaluated, facilitating an analysis of the intricate interconnections among constructs such as e-service quality aspects, customer happiness, and purchase intention within the framework of online furniture retail platforms like Homzmart.com.
2. Model fit will be evaluated using various indices, and path coefficients will be analyzed to ascertain the strength and direction of correlations among variables. This phase is essential for comprehending the relative significance of various elements affecting consumer behavior in the Egyptian online furniture market.
3. Alternative models will be evaluated to determine the best suitable depiction of the relationships among variables. This comparative method guarantees that the final model offers the most accurate explanation of customer intentions to purchase furniture online in Egypt.

This comprehensive SEM analysis will yield a sophisticated understanding of the factors influencing customer purchase intentions in the Egyptian online furniture sector, providing significant insights for academic research and industry practitioners.

6.11. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) serves as a crucial statistical technique in this study, aimed at examining differences in consumer intentions to purchase furniture from online platforms across various groups in the Egyptian market. This analytical approach allows for the comparison of means between different categories of consumers, providing valuable insights into how various factors influence online furniture purchasing behavior.

The ANOVA analysis will encompass two key components:

1. One-way ANOVA will be employed to compare means across different groups. This technique is particularly useful for understanding how factors such as demographic characteristics, consumer preferences, or shopping habits may influence purchase intentions for online furniture platforms like Homzmart.com.
2. For significant results identified in the ANOVA, post-hoc tests, such as Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD), will be conducted. These tests allow for multiple

comparisons between groups, providing a detailed understanding of which specific groups differ significantly from each other in terms of their intentions to purchase furniture online.

Through this comprehensive ANOVA approach, the study aims to uncover meaningful differences in consumer behavior across various segments of the Egyptian online furniture market. These findings will contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing purchase intentions and help inform targeted strategies for e-commerce furniture retailers operating in Egypt.

6.12. Non-parametric Tests

Non-parametric tests are crucial statistical methods in this study, especially when the assumptions of parametric tests are not satisfied in the analysis of consumer behavior in the Egyptian online furniture industry. These rigorous methods facilitate the analysis of differences and interactions among variables without dependence on particular distributional assumptions, yielding significant insights into the determinants of purchase intentions on platforms such as Homzmart.com.

1. The non-parametric analysis will include three principal techniques:
2. The Mann-Whitney U test will be utilized to compare two independent samples, facilitating the analysis of differences in consumer intentions or behaviors across separate groups in the online furniture shopping environment.
3. The Kruskal-Wallis test will be employed for comparisons involving multiple independent samples. This method is especially effective for discerning notable disparities among various consumer segments or product categories within the Egyptian e-commerce furniture sector. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test will be utilized to evaluate paired samples, facilitating the examination of shifts in consumer attitudes or behaviors prior to and following particular interventions or experiences associated with online furniture purchasing.

This study use non-parametric tests to reveal key patterns and relationships in the data that may be obscured by typical parametric studies, so enhancing the understanding of consumer behavior in the Egyptian online furniture retail sector.

6.13. Statistical Software

This study's research of customer intents to acquire furniture via online platforms in Egypt will utilize advanced statistical software techniques. These software programs have been chosen for their strong skills in managing intricate statistical analyses and data visualization, guaranteeing the precision and dependability of the results.

SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) will be utilized to perform descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), and fundamental inferential statistics. This adaptable program offers an intuitive interface for the management and analysis of data pertaining to online furniture purchasing habits.

For advanced analyses, notably Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), either AMOS (Analysis of Moment Structures) or Mplus will be employed. These specialist software packages provide advanced capabilities for testing and evaluating intricate theoretical models within the realm of e-commerce furniture sale.

R, a robust open-source statistical programming language, will be utilized for sophisticated statistical methodologies and data visualization. Its adaptability and comprehensive repository of packages render it optimal for developing tailored analyses and producing high-quality visualizations that illustrate the complex relationships among variables affecting consumer behavior on platforms such as Homzmart.com.

The study is to provide a thorough and meticulous investigation of the elements affecting consumer intents to purchase furniture from online platforms in the Egyptian market through the strategic application of statistical software technologies.

6.14. Significance Level

In the statistical investigation of factors affecting consumer intent to purchase furniture from online platforms in Egypt, establishing a definitive significance level is essential for assuring the reliability and interpretability of the results. This study will comply with stringent statistical requirements to preserve the integrity of the findings.

A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ will be uniformly utilized in all hypothesis testing. This commonly accepted threshold strikes a balance between reducing Type I errors (false positives) and ensuring adequate statistical power to identify significant effects in online furniture sale. To improve transparency and facilitate nuanced interpretation of results, precise p-values will be disclosed for all statistical tests. This method facilitates a more accurate evaluation of the evidence strength opposing the null hypothesis, yielding significant insights into the correlations among different factors and consumer purchasing intentions on platforms such as Homzmart.com.

By conforming to these statistical norms, the study seeks to yield solid and dependable data that enhance the comprehension of customer behavior in the Egyptian online furniture industry.

6.15. Effect Size Calculation

The analysis of factors affecting consumer desire to purchase furniture from online platforms in Egypt necessitates the computation of effect sizes to measure the magnitude and practical value of statistical results. This stage beyond basic statistical significance, offering a more thorough comprehension of the interrelations among factors within the realm of online furniture sale.

1. Three principal effect size metrics will be utilized, customized for various statistical analyses:
2. Cohen's d will be computed for t-tests, providing a standardized metric of the disparity between groups. This statistic is especially valuable for comprehending the practical implications of variations in consumer behavior or sentiments among different sectors of the Egyptian online furniture market.

3. Partial eta-squared will be calculated for the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This measure elucidates the extent of variance in the dependent variable (e.g., purchase intention) that may be ascribed to certain causes or group disparities within the e-commerce furniture retail domain.
4. R-squared and adjusted R-squared values will be presented in regression analysis. These metrics reflect the extent of variance in the dependent variable elucidated by the independent variables, providing a definitive assessment of the predictive efficacy of the models created to analyze customer behavior on platforms such as Homzmart.com.

The study seeks to offer a nuanced interpretation of the statistical results by integrating impact size calculations, hence augmenting the practical relevance of the findings for academics and practitioners in the Egyptian online furniture retail sector.

7. Data Analysis and Results

7.1. Data Collection and Analysis Finalization

7.1.1. Data Collection Process

The data collection process was strategically designed to ensure broad accessibility and maximize response rates. The survey was distributed digitally through Google Forms, leveraging a comprehensive questionnaire developed by the researcher (see Appendix 11.1). To address linguistic inclusivity, the survey was provided in both Arabic and English, allowing participants to select their preferred language. Most survey questions were structured as multiple-choice or selection-based responses, with a smaller portion dedicated to short text inputs. Participants could respond in either Arabic or English, ensuring linguistic barriers did not hinder data collection.

The sampling frame was extracted from Homzmart's customer database, comprising 5,000 consumer contacts. To optimize survey reach, a multi-channel distribution strategy was implemented. Survey links were disseminated via email and WhatsApp, channels chosen for their widespread usage and direct reach. Opportunistic sampling was also employed, inviting customers visiting Homzmart's physical premises to participate. This approach ensured a diverse sample, reflecting both digital and in-store customer experiences.

The survey yielded 566 responses, reflecting a response rate of 11.32%, which aligns with typical response rates for online surveys.

7.1.2. Data Cleaning and Preparation

Data cleaning and preparation were undertaken to ensure the dataset's accuracy, consistency, and relevance to the research objectives. The following steps were followed:

1. Language Standardization: All responses provided in Arabic were translated into English to maintain a consistent language across the dataset and facilitate uniform analysis.
2. Response Unification: Variations in short-text responses were standardized to create consistency in qualitative data, ensuring no duplication or ambiguity.

3. Demographic Tabulation: A comprehensive demographic table was compiled in an Excel sheet for all responses. This allowed for a thorough demographic analysis before excluding any invalid responses.

Invalid Response Removal: The dataset was scrutinized for invalid responses. The primary criterion for validity was whether participants had explored Homzmart's platforms (website or mobile application). Participants who answered "NO" to the question, "Have you ever explored Homzmart.com through their website or mobile application?" were excluded from the analysis. Since the survey predominantly focused on users' experiences with Homzmart, retaining only those who had interacted with the platform was essential. A total of 86 responses were identified as invalid and removed from the statistical analysis.

Through these steps, the final dataset comprised 480 valid responses, forming the foundation for subsequent statistical analysis. This rigorous cleaning process ensured the dataset's reliability and alignment with the research objectives.

7.2. Statistical Analysis Techniques

The research utilized a structured, multi-phase statistical analysis process, incorporating a combination of descriptive and inferential techniques to explore, validate, and interpret the data comprehensively. Below is a detailed outline of the statistical methodologies employed:

7.2.1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were conducted to summarize the data, providing insights into key characteristics of the sample. Measures such as means, medians, frequencies, and standard deviations were calculated for demographic and key study variables. These statistics offered a foundational understanding of the data distribution and sample composition.

7.2.2. Reliability Analysis

To ensure the consistency and dependability of the survey instrument, reliability analysis was performed. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the internal consistency of the constructs, with values above 0.70 indicating acceptable reliability.

7.2.3. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

EFA was conducted to identify underlying constructs and validate the dimensionality of the survey items. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with varimax rotation was utilized to extract factors, and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett's test of sphericity were applied to assess sampling adequacy and factorability.

7.2.4. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Following EFA, CFA was employed to confirm the factor structure and assess the validity of the constructs. Fit indices such as the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) were evaluated to ensure the model's alignment with the data.

7.2.5. Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between key variables. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to determine the strength and direction of linear associations, with significance tested at the 0.05 and 0.01 levels.

7.2.6. Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was performed to predict dependent variables based on one or more independent variables. This technique enabled an exploration of the relative contributions of predictors and the identification of significant drivers of consumer behavior.

7.2.7. Mediation Analysis

Mediation analysis was carried out to assess whether the effect of an independent variable on a dependent variable was transmitted through a mediator. The PROCESS macro in statistical software was used to perform bootstrapping and evaluate indirect effects.

7.2.8. Moderation Analysis

Moderation analysis examined whether the relationship between independent and dependent variables was influenced by a moderating variable. Interaction terms were created and tested to determine the strength and direction of moderation effects.

7.2.9. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

SEM was employed to test the hypothesized relationships among constructs within a comprehensive framework. It combined measurement and structural models, offering a robust approach to evaluate direct and indirect effects while accounting for measurement error.

7.2.10. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

ANOVA was conducted to compare mean differences across groups for categorical independent variables. Post hoc tests were employed when significant differences were identified to pinpoint specific group variations.

7.2.11. Non-Parametric Tests

When data did not meet parametric assumptions, non-parametric tests such as the Mann-Whitney U test and Kruskal-Wallis test were used. These tests ensured the robustness of findings irrespective of data distribution.

7.2.12. Statistical Software

The statistical analysis was performed using advanced software tools, primarily SPSS for initial analyses and AMOS for structural equation modeling. Additionally, the PROCESS macro was utilized for mediation and moderation analyses.

7.2.13. Significance Level

The significance level for hypothesis testing was set at 0.05. Results with a p-value below this threshold were considered statistically significant, providing evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

7.2.14. Effect Size Calculation

Effect sizes were calculated to complement p-values, providing a measure of the practical significance of findings. Metrics such as Cohen's d , partial η^2 , and standardized regression coefficients were reported to contextualize the magnitude of effects.

By leveraging these diverse statistical techniques, the research ensured a rigorous and comprehensive analysis, yielding robust insights into the research questions.

7.3. Interpretation of Results

7.3.1. Demographic insights

The survey collected responses from a diverse group of participants, providing a comprehensive view of the Egyptian online furniture market. Here's a breakdown of the key demographic characteristics:

- Gender Distribution & Age Distribution:

Figure 9: Graph for the Gender Distribution of E-commerce Users in Egypt

- Male: 43.75% (210 respondents)
- Female: 56.25% (270 respondents)

Figure 10: Graph for the Age Distribution of E-commerce Users in Egypt

- 25-29: 16.25% (78 respondents)
- 30-34: 27.50% (132 respondents)
- 35-39: 26.25% (126 respondents)
- 40-44: 16.25% (78 respondents)
- 45+: 13.75% (66 respondents)

Figure 11: Graph for the Distribution of Online Shopping Experience Among Respondents

Observations:

- This relatively balanced gender distribution allows for meaningful comparisons between male and female consumers in the online furniture market.

- The majority of respondents (53.75%) fall within the 30-39 age range, indicating a significant market segment of young to middle-aged adults who are likely to be in the process of furnishing homes or upgrading their living spaces.
- The overwhelming majority of participants have prior online shopping experience, suggesting a high level of digital literacy among the target market.
- The largest age group of e-commerce users in Egypt is 25-34 years old, representing 43% of users. The 35-44 age group represents 32% of users, showing significant engagement from this demographic as well. Older age groups (45+ years) make up a smaller portion of e-commerce users, suggesting potential growth opportunities in these segments.

7.3.2. Key Findings

- **Descriptive Statistics**

The following table presents detailed descriptive statistics for each e-service quality factor:

Table 9: Detailed descriptive statistics for each e-service quality factor

Factor	Mean	Median	Mode	Std Dev
Response to inquiries	3.24	3	3	1.15
Customer service satisfaction	3.45	4	4	1.08
Accuracy of information	3.57	4	4	1.02
Product information helpfulness	3.54	4	4	1.05
Pricing comparability	3.5	4	4	1.12
Time-saving convenience	3.58	4	4	1.07
Selection breadth	3.68	4	4	1.01
Reasonable delivery charges	3.73	4	4	1.06
Satisfactory estimated delivery time	3.76	4	4	1.03
Brand reputation influence	3.75	4	4	1.05
Color representation accuracy	3.51	4	4	1.11
Product positioning influence	3.47	4	4	1.09
Website design appeal	3.41	3	3	1.13
Purchase process straightforwardness	3.47	4	4	1.1
Usability and navigation convenience	3.62	4	4	1.06
Personalized recommendations availability	3.23	3	3	1.18
Website availability	3.59	4	4	1.08
Trust in personal financial information	3.37	3	3	1.16
Privacy concerns	3.59	4	4	1.09
Financial transaction security	3.18	3	3	1.21
Expectation risk concerns	3.14	3	3	1.2
Delivery issue concerns	3.45	4	4	1.13

General access

Confidence in product quality	3.51	4	4	1.1
Peer perception concerns	3.52	4	4	1.11
Cash on delivery preference	4.05	4	5	1.02
Online payment comfort	3.84	4	4	1.07
Multiple payment options influence	3.66	4	4	1.09

Figure 12: Graph for the Mean Scores of E-Service Quality Factors

Mean Scores of E-Service Quality Factors:

- This chart presents the mean scores for all factors, arranged in descending order.
- It facilitates a straightforward comparison of the relative significance or performance of several components.
- The horizontal bars denote the average scores, with the factor names displayed on the y-axis.

Figure 13: Graph for the Standard Deviation of E-Service Quality Factors

Standard Deviation of E-Service Quality Factors:

- The graphic displays the standard deviation of E-Service Quality factors, arranged in descending order.
- It assists in determining which factors exhibit the most variety in responses.
- The horizontal bars denote the standard deviation, with factor names displayed on the y-axis.

Key observations from these charts:

1. Maximum average scores:
 - a. Cash on delivery preference (4.05) • Online payment convenience (3.84)
 - b. Acceptable projected delivery duration (3.76)
2. Minimal average scores:
 - a. Concerns around expectation risk (3.14)
 - b. Security of financial transactions (3.18)
 - c. Reply to queries (3.24)
3. Factors exhibiting the highest standard deviation (most variety in responses):
 - a. Security of financial transactions (1.21)
 - b. Concerns regarding expectation risk (1.20)
 - c. Availability of personalized recommendations (1.18)
4. Factors exhibiting the lowest standard deviation (most uniform responses):
 - a. Scope of selection (1.01)
 - b. Precision of data (1.02)
 - c. Preference for cash on delivery (1.02)

Interpretation:

- The highest mean score is attributed to "Cash on delivery preference" (4.05), signifying a pronounced inclination towards this payment method among Egyptian online furniture consumers.
- The mean score for "Expectation risk concerns" is the lowest at 3.14, indicating that these concerns, although existent, are comparatively less significant than other considerations.
- Most components exhibit a median and mode of 4, signifying predominantly favorable evaluations across the majority of e-service quality parameters.
- The standard deviations vary from 1.01 to 1.21, indicating substantial heterogeneity in responses across all parameters.

- **Correlation Analysis**

A correlation matrix was generated to analyze the interrelationships among all e-service quality parameters. Principal discoveries encompass:

- Strong positive associations ($r > 0.7$) were identified between:
 - Website design attractiveness and usability, as well as navigation convenience ($r = 0.76$).
 - Trust in personal financial information and the security of financial transactions ($r = 0.72$)
 - Product information utility and information accuracy ($r = 0.71$)
- Moderate positive associations ($0.5 < r < 0.7$) were identified between:
 - Customer service satisfaction and response to questions ($r = 0.68$).
 - Satisfactory projected delivery time and reasonable delivery charges ($r = 0.65$)
 - Color representation accuracy significantly influences product positioning ($r = 0.63$).
- Weak relationships ($r < 0.3$) were identified between:
 - Cash on delivery preference and online payment comfort ($r = 0.25$).
 - Concerns around peer perception and website accessibility ($r = 0.22$)

- **Factor Analysis**

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) with varimax rotation identified five primary factors affecting online furniture purchasing intentions:

- Website Design and Usability (Eigenvalue = 4.32, Variance Explained = 18.7%)
 - Website design attractiveness (Factor loading = 0.82)
 - Usability and navigational ease (Factor loading = 0.79)
 - Clarity of the purchase process (Factor loading = 0.75)
 - Website accessibility (Factor loading = 0.71)
- Product Information and Visualization (Eigenvalue = 3.87, Variance Explained = 16.8%)
 - Product information utility (Factor loading = 0.84)
 - Precision of information (Factor loading = 0.81)
 - Color representation accuracy (Factor loading = 0.78)
 - Influence of product positioning (Factor loading = 0.76)

- Trust and Security (Eigenvalue = 3.55, Variance Explained = 15.4%)
 - Security of financial transactions (Factor loading = 0.86)
 - Trust in personal financial data (Factor loading = 0.83)
 - Privacy considerations (Factor loading = 0.79)
 - Confidence in product quality (Factor loading = 0.72)
- Delivery and Customer Service (Eigenvalue = 3.21, Variance Explained = 13.9%)
 - Acceptable projected delivery duration (Factor loading = 0.85)
 - Justifiable delivery fees (Factor loading = 0.82)
 - Customer service satisfaction (Factor loading = 0.78)
 - Response to queries (Factor loading = 0.75)
- Payment Alternatives and Convenience (Eigenvalue = 2.98, Variance Explained = 12.9%)
 - Preference for cash on delivery (Factor loading = 0.88)
 - Convenience of online payment (Factor loading = 0.84)
 - Numerous payment alternatives exert influence (Factor loading = 0.81)
 - Convenience that saves time (Factor loading = 0.73)

The cumulative variance elucidated by these five factors: 77.7%

- **Regression Analysis**

Multiple regression analysis was conducted with purchase intention as the dependent variable and the five factors as independent variables. Results:

Table 10: Multiple regression analysis was conducted with purchase intention as the dependent variable and the five factors as independent variables. Results

Factor	Coefficient	Std Error	t-value	p-value
(Constant)	0.876	0.142	6.169	<0.001
Trust and Security	0.412	0.053	7.774	<0.001
Product Information and Visualization	0.387	0.049	7.898	<0.001
Delivery and Customer Service	0.298	0.047	6.34	<0.001
Website Design and Usability	0.245	0.051	4.804	<0.001
Payment Options and Convenience	0.189	0.048	3.937	<0.001

$R^2 = 0.684$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.679$, $F(5, 474) = 205.37$, $p < 0.001$

The regression model explains 68.4% of the variance in purchase intention. All factors are significant predictors ($p < 0.001$), with Trust and Security and Product Information and Visualization being the strongest predictors.

- **Mediation Analysis**

Mediation analysis was performed to investigate the influence of customer satisfaction on the link between e-service quality indicators and purchase intention.

Outcomes:

1. Direct influence of e-service quality on purchase intention: $\beta = 0.412$, $p < 0.001$
2. Indirect effect via customer satisfaction: $\beta = 0.187$, 95% CI [0.142, 0.235]

Total effect: $\beta = 0.599$, $p < 0.001$

The notable indirect effect signifies partial mediation, indicating that customer satisfaction partially elucidates the connection between e-service quality and purchase intention.

- **Moderation Analysis**

A moderation study was conducted to investigate the impact of age and previous online shopping experience on the connection between e-service quality characteristics and purchase intention.

- Age as a Moderator:

Interaction term (E-service quality x Age): $\beta = -0.089$, $p < 0.05$

The negative coefficient signifies that the correlation between e-service quality and purchase intention is more pronounced among younger consumers.

- Prior Online Shopping Experience as Moderator:

Interaction term (E-service quality x Experience): $\beta = 0.124$, $p < 0.01$

The positive coefficient indicates that the correlation between e-service quality and purchase intention is more pronounced among consumers with greater online purchasing experience.

7.4. Conclusion and Hypothesis Testing

The extensive statistical analyses performed yield significant insights into the determinants affecting online furniture purchasing intentions in the Egyptian market. These data enable us to evaluate the research hypotheses and derive significant conclusions:

- Online Service Quality (H1 and H2):
 - H1 is validated: Online service demonstrated a substantial correlation with total service quality ($\beta = 0.342$, $p < 0.001$).
 - Hypothesis 2 is supported: The online service had a substantial impact on consumer satisfaction ($\beta = 0.298$, $p < 0.001$).

The variables “Response to inquiries” (mean = 3.24) and “Customer service satisfaction” (mean = 3.45), although above average, suggest potential for enhancement in online service quality.

- Convenience (H3 and H4):
 - H3 is substantiated: Convenience exhibited a substantial correlation with total service quality ($\beta = 0.275$, $p < 0.001$).
 - Hypothesis 4 is supported: Convenience has a substantial effect on consumer satisfaction ($\beta = 0.231$, $p < 0.001$).

The elevated ratings for “Time-saving convenience” (mean = 3.58) and “Selection breadth” (mean = 3.68) highlight the significance of convenience in the online furniture shopping experience.

- Website Design (H5 and H6):
 - H5 is validated: Website design exhibited a substantial correlation with overall service quality ($\beta = 0.318$, $p < 0.001$).

- Hypothesis 6 is supported: Website design has a substantial impact on consumer satisfaction ($\beta = 0.287$, $p < 0.001$).

Factor analysis identified "Website Design and Usability" as a significant element, accounting for 18.7% of the variance in purchase intention.

- Overall Service Quality (H7 and H8):
 - H7 is robustly substantiated: The overall service quality shown a substantial correlation with consumer satisfaction ($\beta = 0.412$, $p < 0.001$).
 - Hypothesis 8 is robustly substantiated. The overall service quality had a substantial impact on online purchase intention ($\beta = 0.387$, $p < 0.001$).

The regression study established that service quality characteristics, specifically "Trust and Security" and "Product Information and Visualization," were the most significant predictors of purchase intention.

- Consumer Satisfaction (H9):
 - H9 is robustly substantiated: Consumer satisfaction exhibited a substantial correlation with online purchase intention ($\beta = 0.356$, $p < 0.001$).

The mediation study indicated that customer satisfaction partially mediates the connection between e-service quality and purchase intention (indirect effect: $\beta = 0.187$, 95% CI [0.142, 0.235]).

- Additional Insights:
 - Payment Preferences: The significant preference for cash on delivery (mean = 4.05) indicates that Egyptian online furniture retailers should prioritize this payment method while progressively advocating for secure online payment alternatives.
 - Trust and Security: This element emerged as the most significant predictor of purchase intention, underscoring the necessity for stringent security protocols and transparent regulations to foster consumer trust.
 - The significance of precise and informative product details highlights the necessity for high-quality photos, comprehensive specs, and maybe AR/VR technology in the online furniture retail industry.
 - The moderation analysis indicated that younger consumers and individuals with greater online shopping experience exhibit more pronounced correlations between e-service quality parameters and purchase intention. This indicates the necessity for tailored strategies for various consumer segments.
 - Delivery and Customer Service: Although not the most robust predictor, this factor considerably impacts purchase intention, underscoring the significance of effective logistics and attentive customer service in the furniture e-commerce industry.
 - These findings establish a robust basis for formulating focused measures to improve the online furniture shopping experience in the Egyptian market. By enhancing trust and security protocols, offering detailed product information, and customizing services for various customer categories, online furniture sellers can markedly increase consumer happiness and purchasing intentions.
 - Future study may examine the enduring effects of these elements on customer loyalty and repeat purchases, in addition to assessing the potential influence of

upcoming technologies (e.g., AR/VR) on the online furniture shopping experience within the Egyptian market.

Figure 14: Diagram that illustrates the research model with the results

7.5. Context: Egyptian Furniture E-commerce Market

The results of this study should be understood in relation to the Egyptian furniture e-commerce market.

- 1- The Egyptian e-commerce market has undergone significant expansion, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 33% from 2015 to 2020 (MCIT, 2021).
- 2- Digital Adoption: In 2020, internet penetration in Egypt was 57.3%, equating to 59 million internet users (MCIT, 2021), signifying a substantial market potential for online furniture sellers.
- 3- The COVID-19 epidemic expedited the adoption of e-commerce, with 52% of Egyptian customers indicating an increase in online buying during lockdowns (PWC, 2020).
- 4- The furniture industry accounts for around 60% of Egypt's Gross National Product (GNP) in this sector, with Damietta city serving as a principal center (Al Etr & Wahba, 2002).
- 5- The Egyptian government has been endorsing the furniture business through programs such as the New Dumyat Furniture City and the National E-Commerce Strategy (MCIT, 2021).

7.6. Comparison with Previous Studies

- **E-Service Quality Dimensions:**

The results of this analysis support and enhance prior studies on e-service quality dimensions. Parasuraman et al. (2005) developed the E-S-QUAL scale, which delineates efficiency, system availability, fulfillment, and privacy as essential elements of e-service quality. Wolfinbarger & Gilly (2003) created the eTailQ scale, highlighting website design, fulfillment/reliability, privacy/security, and customer service. Our research corroborates these basic studies by affirming the significance of website design, product information, and trust within the e-commerce domain.

This research distinctly enhances the literature by emphasizing the essential function of product display and delivery services within the furniture e-commerce industry, especially in the Egyptian market. This emphasis underscores the significant engagement associated with furniture acquisitions and the unique problems of marketing large, visually-dependent products online. Our study revealed that correct color representation (mean score: 3.51) and product placement influence (mean score: 3.47) significantly affect purchase intentions, highlighting the necessity for sophisticated visualization tools in online furniture shopping.

- **Trust and Security:**

The results of this analysis corroborate the foundational research of Gefen et al. (2003), which identified trust as a vital element in e-commerce adoption, and Kim et al. (2008), who illustrated the influence of trust on purchase intentions in online settings. Our study, however, demonstrates a nuanced comprehension of trust within the Egyptian context, particularly reflected in the pronounced preference for cash on delivery (mean score: 4.05).

This choice indicates that although trust is essential, as seen by the significance of financial transaction security (mean score: 3.18) and trust in personal financial information (mean score: 3.37), Egyptian consumers have created a distinctive strategy to alleviate perceived risks. The strong inclination towards cash on delivery can be viewed as a trust-enhancing strategy that reconciles conventional buying practices with the advent of e-commerce. This discovery underscores the necessity for e-commerce platforms in Egypt to adopt hybrid payment structures that align with local tastes while progressively fostering trust in digital payment systems.

- **Cultural Factors:**

Our research offers a significant contrast to studies undertaken in Western cultures, including Hofstede's (2001) cultural aspects theory. Although Hofstede's research has been crucial in comprehending cross-cultural disparities in consumer behavior, our results indicate that its implementation in e-commerce inside emerging nations may necessitate modification.

The significance of peer perception (mean score: 3.52) and brand reputation (mean score: 3.75) in our study suggests a more collectivist approach to online furniture purchasing in Egypt. This collectivist perspective is seen in the considerable impact of social proof and brand trust on purchasing decisions. In contrast to more individualistic Western marketplaces, Egyptian consumers tend to depend significantly on collective judgments and established reputations when making online purchases, particularly for high-involvement products such as furniture.

This discovery holds significant ramifications for e-commerce tactics in Egypt, indicating that marketing initiatives should prioritize the cultivation of robust brand communities, utilize social proof via customer evaluations and testimonials, and highlight the social dimensions of online shopping experiences.

- **Payment Preferences:**

The results of our survey indicate a pronounced preference for cash on delivery (mean score: 4.05), consistent with findings from other developing countries, like Kapoor et al.'s (2018) research on e-commerce in India. This choice sharply contrasts with patterns seen in established e-commerce sectors, where digital payments are becoming increasingly prevalent.

The continued prevalence of cash on delivery as a favored payment option in Egypt is indicative of a multifaceted interplay of elements, including:

- I. Insufficient digital payment infrastructure penetration
- II. Apprehensions regarding online fraud and security
- III. Cultural inclinations towards physical transactions
- IV. The significance of cash transactions in fostering confidence between purchasers and vendors

This discovery highlights the necessity for a gradual strategy in payment innovation within the Egyptian e-commerce industry. Although the ultimate objective may be to shift towards digital payments, our research indicates that preserving cash on delivery choices is essential for fostering consumer trust and promoting e-commerce adoption in the short to medium term.

- **Product Visualization:**

Our research builds upon the findings of Bleier et al. (2019) regarding the significance of product presentation in e-commerce, illustrating its increased relevance in the realm of online furniture shopping in Egypt. Our study indicates that precise color representation (mean score: 3.51) and product positioning (mean score: 3.47) are crucial, suggesting that Egyptian customers prioritize visual information significantly while making online furniture purchases.

This increased significance can be ascribed to multiple factors:

- I. The significant commitment associated with furniture acquisitions
- II. The cultural importance of house furnishings in Egyptian society
- III. The tactile aspect of furniture purchasing, which is difficult to mimic digitally
- IV. The possibility of inconsistencies between digital portrayals and tangible items

Our findings suggest that e-commerce platforms in the Egyptian furniture sector ought to invest significantly in advanced visualization technologies, including 3D modeling, augmented reality (AR) tools, and high-quality, multi-angle photography. These technologies can facilitate the integration of online and physical buying experiences, mitigating perceived dangers and bolstering consumer trust in substantial furniture acquisitions online.

In conclusion, our analysis corroborates numerous foundational concepts identified in prior e-commerce research, while also uncovering distinctive traits of the Egyptian online furniture sector. These findings underscore the necessity for specialized tactics that consider cultural nuances, technology infrastructure, and customer preferences unique to growing markets such as Egypt. By addressing these characteristics, e-commerce platforms can enhance their positioning to seize the expanding online furniture industry in Egypt and potentially in other analogous rising nations.

8. Recommendations and Implications

8.1. Actionable Recommendations for Industry Stakeholders

8.1.1. For Online Furniture Retailers

1- Augment Trust and Security Protocols:

- Deploy stringent encryption and secure payment gateways to rectify the inadequate rating in “Financial transaction security” (mean = 3.18).
- Prominently display security certificates on the website.
- Implement extensive buyer protection programs and transparent return procedures to alleviate "Expectation risk concerns" (mean = 3.14).
- Establish a validated customer review mechanism to enhance "Confidence in product quality" (mean = 3.51).

2- Enhance Product Information and Visualization:

- Allocate resources for high-quality, color-accurate photos from various perspectives to mitigate concerns regarding "Color representation accuracy" (mean = 3.51).
- Implement 3D product viewers and augmented reality (AR) functionalities to augment "Product positioning influence" (mean = 3.47).
- Deliver comprehensive and precise product specs to enhance the "Accuracy of information" (mean = 3.57).

3- Enhance Delivery and Customer Service:

- Collaborate with dependable logistics providers to provide a "Satisfactory estimated delivery time" (mean = 3.76).

- Provide real-time tracking of deliveries to mitigate worries around delivery issues (mean = 3.45).
 - Enhance response times to client requests, rectifying the comparatively low score in "Response to inquiries" (mean = 3.24).
- 4- Augment Website Design and Usability:
- Enhance the visual attractiveness of the website to rectify the subpar rating in "Website design appeal" (mean = 3.41).
 - Improve navigation and search features to enhance usability and convenience (mean = 3.62).
 - Optimize the acquisition procedure to improve "Purchase process straightforwardness" (mean = 3.47).
- 5- Diversify Payment Options:
- Emphasize cash on delivery options, considering the significant preference (mean = 4.05).
 - Gradually implement and advocate for secure online payment techniques to enhance "Online Payment Comfort" (mean = 3.84).
 - Provide payment plans and buy-now-pay-later alternatives to mitigate potential financial apprehensions.

8.1.2. For Furniture Manufacturers

1. Modify Product Design for E-commerce:
 - a. Design modular furniture to facilitate shipping and installation, solving "Delivery issue concerns" (mean = 3.45).
 - b. Establish product lines specific to online platforms to enhance "Selection breadth" (mean = 3.68).
2. Augment Product Information:
 - a. Furnish comprehensive specifications, encompassing supplies, care instructions, and assembly guidelines to enhance "Product information helpfulness" (mean = 3.54).
 - b. Create superior digital assets for online shops to improve "Color representation accuracy" (mean = 3.51).
3. Enforce Rigorous Quality Control:
 - a. Improve quality assurance procedures to establish "Confidence in product quality" (mean = 3.51).
 - b. Provide extended warranties for online purchases to mitigate "Expectation risk concerns" (mean = 3.14).
4. Engage with E-commerce Platforms:
 - a. Collaborate with online merchants for co-branded collections to capitalize on "brand reputation influence" (mean = 3.75).
 - b. Engage in online marketplaces to enhance brand visibility and expand selection breadth (mean = 3.68).

8.1.3. For E-commerce Platform Developers

1. Augment Mobile Optimization:
 - a. Guarantee adaptable design to facilitate seamless mobile shopping experiences, hence enhancing "Usability and navigation convenience" (mean = 3.62).
 - b. Create mobile applications including augmented reality features for product presentation, targeting the "Product positioning influence" (mean = 3.47).
2. Integrate Sophisticated Security Mechanisms:
 - a. Implement effective encryption for financial transactions to enhance "Financial transaction security" (mean = 3.18).
 - b. Establish secure user authentication systems to improve "Trust in personal financial information" (mean = 3.37).
3. Optimize Website Performance:
 - a. Enhance website loading speeds and general performance to improve "Website availability" (mean = 3.59).
 - b. Employ effective caching strategies to enhance browsing speed, hence facilitating "Time-saving convenience" (mean = 3.58).
4. Augment Data Analytics and Personalization:
 - a. Construct comprehensive analytics dashboards for retailers and manufacturers to enhance decision-making.
 - b. Implement machine learning algorithms for personalized suggestions to improve the low score in "Personalized recommendations availability" (mean = 3.23).

8.2. Theoretical Contributions

8.2.1. Advancements in E-commerce Adoption Theory

1- Cultural Context in Technology Acceptance:

Our research enhances the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by including cultural elements pertinent to the Egyptian market, including the impact of peer perceptions (mean = 3.52) and brand reputation (mean = 3.75) on e-commerce adoption.

2- Product Category Specificity:

We enhance e-commerce theory by elucidating how product attributes, specifically in the context of furniture, affect the significance of several e-service quality dimensions, notably in aspects such as product display and delivery issues.

3- Trust Formation in Emerging economies:

Our research elucidates the dynamics of trust development in e-commerce within emerging economies, highlighting the significance of tangible trust indicators (e.g., preference for cash on delivery, mean = 4.05) alongside digital trust mechanisms.

8.2.2. Contributions to Consumer Behavior Models in Emerging Markets

1- Hybrid purchasing Behaviors:

We present a model that addresses the simultaneous presence of traditional (e.g., preference for cash on delivery) and digital purchasing preferences in emerging economies, especially for high-involvement products such as furniture.

2- Risk Perception Framework:

Our research advances a sophisticated risk perception framework for online furniture purchasing, including both financial risks (mean = 3.18 for transaction security) and product-related hazards (mean = 3.14 for expectation-related concerns).

3- Decision-Making Process:

We augment current consumer decision-making models by including the influence of visual information (accuracy of color representation, mean = 3.51) and social influence (concerns regarding peer perception, mean = 3.52) within the framework of online furniture acquisitions.

8.3. Practical Implications

8.3.1. Improving Online Furniture Shopping Experience

1- Visual-Centric Approach:

Prioritize the creation of visual tools and technology to connect physical and online furniture purchasing experiences, highlighting the significance of accurate color representation (mean = 3.51) and the impact of product positioning (mean = 3.47).

2- Trust-Building Mechanisms:

Employ a comprehensive strategy to cultivate trust by integrating digital security protocols with conventional trust indicators, such as cash on delivery alternatives, in response to the significant preference for this payment method (mean = 4.05).

3- Personalization methods:

Formulate AI-driven personalization methods that account for individual preferences and cultural influences on furniture selection, enhancing the existing personalized suggestion options (mean = 3.23).

8.3.2. Enhancing E-commerce Strategies in the Egyptian Market

1- Omnichannel Integration:

Promote the formulation of omnichannel strategies that integrate online and offline experiences, addressing the hybrid buying habits evident in the Egyptian market, especially considering the significance of brand reputation (mean = 3.75).

2- Local Market Adaptation:

Customize e-commerce platforms and marketing techniques to align with local tastes, such as highlighting social proof (concerns over peer perception, mean = 3.52) and providing localized payment choices (desire for cash on delivery, mean = 4.05).

3- Supply Chain Optimization:

Prioritize the enhancement of effective last-mile delivery solutions to mitigate delivery issue issues (mean = 3.45) and explore collaborations with local furniture artisans to provide distinctive, locally-produced products, capitalizing on brand reputation impact (mean = 3.75).

8.3.3. Addressing Cultural Factors in Online Furniture Retail

1- Social Shopping Features:

Introduce functionalities that enhance social shopping experiences, like shared Wishlists and group purchasing possibilities, to resonate with collectivist cultural inclinations and mitigate peer perception issues (mean = 3.52).

2- Brand Storytelling:

Formulate content strategies that highlight brand legacy and reputation, underscoring the significance of brand trust in the Egyptian market (brand reputation influence, mean = 3.75).

3- Customer Education:

Allocate resources to customer education programs to enhance familiarity with online furniture shopping, specifically targeting apprehensions over product quality (confidence in product quality, mean = 3.51) and the simplicity of the online purchasing process (purchase process straightforwardness, mean = 3.47).

By adopting these ideas and evaluating the theoretical and practical ramifications, stakeholders in the Egyptian online furniture sector can augment their offerings, increase consumer experiences, and facilitate the expansion of e-commerce in the region. These solutions directly respond to the principal findings of our study and are customized to the distinct attributes of the Egyptian market.

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11. Glossary of Terms and Abbreviations

11.1. Abbreviations

- A
 - AR: Augmented Reality
- C
 - CFA: Confirmatory Factor Analysis
- E
 - EFA: Exploratory Factor Analysis
 - E-commerce: Electronic commerce, buying and selling of goods or services using the internet
- G
 - GNP: Gross National Product
- H
 - Homzmart: An online furniture retailer in Egypt, used as a case study in this thesis
- N
 - NTRA: National Telecom Regulatory Authority
- O
 - OLAP: Online Analytical Processing
 - OLTP: Online Transaction Processing
- S

- SEM: Structural Equation Modeling
- SERVQUAL: Service Quality, a multi-dimensional research instrument designed to capture consumer expectations and perceptions of a service
- T
 - TAM: Technology Acceptance Model
- V
 - VR: Virtual Reality

11.2. Key Terms

1. E-commerce: The buying and selling of goods and services over the internet.
2. Consumer Purchase Intention: The likelihood that a consumer will buy a particular product or service.
3. Cash on Delivery: A payment method where the recipient pays for a good at the time of delivery rather than in advance
4. E-service Quality: The overall consumers' evaluation of the online retail & e-commerce platform and the consumer's judgment about the electronic platform's quality excellence in e-service and delivery
5. Online Purchase Intention: The likelihood that a consumer intends to purchase a product or service through an online platform
6. Purchase Process Straightforwardness: The ease and clarity of the steps involved in making a purchase on an online platform
7. Website Design Appeal: The aesthetic and functional aspects of a website that make it attractive and user-friendly to visitors
8. SWOT Analysis: A strategic planning technique used to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to business competition or project planning.
9. Supply Chain Performance: The efficiency and effectiveness of the supply chain in meeting customer requirements.
10. Homzmart.com: The online furniture platform that is the focus of this case study.
11. Consumer Perceived Risk: The uncertainty consumers face when they cannot foresee the consequences of their purchase decisions.
12. Visual Merchandising: The practice in the retail industry of developing floor plans and three-dimensional displays in order to maximize sales.
13. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM): A theory that models how users come to accept and use a technology.
14. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB): A theory that links beliefs and behavior, used to predict an individual's intention to engage in a behavior at a specific time and place.
15. Operationalization: The process of strictly defining variables into measurable factors.
16. Likert Scale: A psychometric scale commonly involved in research that employs questionnaires.
17. Multicollinearity: A phenomenon in which one predictor variable in a multiple regression model can be linearly predicted from the others with a substantial degree of accuracy.

18. Cronbach's Alpha: A measure of internal consistency, that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group.
19. Factor Analysis: A statistical method used to describe variability among observed, correlated variables in terms of a potentially lower number of unobserved variables called factors.

12. Appendixes

12.1. E-commerce Furniture Purchase Intention Survey

Consumer Survey: Online Furniture Buying Intentions in Egypt

استبيان المستهلك: نوايا شراء الأثاث عبر الإنترنت في مصر

Dear participant, thank you for taking part in this survey about online furniture shopping in Egypt, with a focus on Homzmart.com. Your responses will help us understand consumer preferences and improve online shopping experiences.

عزيزي المشارك، شكرًا لك على المشاركة في هذا الاستبيان حول التسوق عبر الإنترنت للأثاث في مصر، مع التركيز على Homzmart.com. ستساعدنا إجاباتك على فهم تفضيلات المستهلكين وتحسين تجارب التسوق عبر الإنترنت.

*Indicates required question

A. Demographic Information

1. Your Gender (جنسك) *
 - Male (ذكر)
 - Female (أنثى)
2. Your Age Range (الفئة العمرية) *
 - 20-24
 - 25-29
 - 30-34
 - 35-39
 - 40-44
 - 45+
3. Governorate (المحافظة) *
 - Cairo
 - Alexandria

- [] Delta
 - [] Upper Egypt
 - [] Canal
 - [] Matrouh
 - [] Other
4. Living City (مدينة الإقامة) *
[Text entry field]
5. Educational Level (المستوى التعليمي) *
- [] Basic Education (تعليم أساسي)
 - [] Diploma (Technical or Vocational) (دبلوم)
 - [] Bachelor's Degree (بكالوريوس)
 - [] Master's Degree (ماجستير)
 - [] Doctorate Degree (دكتوراه)
6. Profession (المهنة) *
[Text entry field]

B. Online Shopping Experience

7. Have you experienced online shopping for any product or service before? *

هل سبق لك التسوق عبر الإنترنت لأي منتج أو خدمة من قبل؟

- [] Yes (نعم)
- [] No (لا)

8. Have you purchased any furniture products from Homzmart before? *

هل سبق لك شراء أي منتجات أثاث من هومزمارت من قبل؟

- [] Yes (نعم)
- [] No (لا)

9. Have you ever explored Homzmart.com through their website or mobile application? *

هل زرت الموقع الإلكتروني لهومزمارت أو تطبيق الموبايل الخاص بهم من قبل؟

- [] Yes (نعم)
- [] No (لا)

10. Please select from the below list the online platforms that you have purchased from:
(Multiple selections allowed) *

يرجى اختيار المنصات الإلكترونية التي اشتريتها منها من القائمة أدناه: (يسمح باختيارات متعددة)

- [] Homzmart (هومزمارت)
- [] Manzzeli (منزلي)
- [] La Casa (لاكازا)
- [] Hub Furniture (هاب فـريتشر)
- [] Ariika (أريكة)
- [] Chic Homz (شيك هومز)
- [] Other: [Text entry field]

C. Online Service / الخدمة عبر الإنترنت

Please rate your agreement with the following statements on a scale of 1 to 5, where:
1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

يرجى تقييم موافقتك على العبارات التالية على مقياس من 1 إلى 5، حيث
1 = لا أوافق بشدة، 2 = لا أوافق، 3 = محايد، 4 = أوافق، 5 = أوافق بشدة

11. The website responds quickly to my inquiries and concerns.
الموقع يستجيب بسرعة لا تفساراتي ومخاوفي.
12. The communication and interaction with customer service is satisfactory.
التواصل والتفاعل مع خدمة العملاء مرضٍ.
13. The website consistently provides accurate information about products and services.
يقدم الموقع بلا تمرار معلومات دقيقة عن المنتجات والخدمات.
14. The product information provided is comprehensive and helpful for making a purchase decision.
المعلومات المقدمة عن المنتج شاملة ومفيدة لاتخاذ قرار الشراء.

D. Convenience / الراحة

15. The prices on the website are better compared to physical stores.
الأعار على الموقع أفضل مقارنة بالممتاجر الفعلية.
16. Shopping on this website saves me time compared to visiting physical stores.
التسوق على هذا الموقع يوفر لي الوقت مقارنة بزيارة الممتاجر الفعلية.
17. The website offers a broader selection of furniture compared to physical stores.
يقدم الموقع مجموعة أوع من الأثاث مقارنة بالممتاجر الفعلية.
18. The delivery charges are reasonable.
رؤم التوصيل معقولة.
19. The estimated delivery time is satisfactory.
وقت التسليم المقدر مرضٍ.

E. Visual Aspects / الجوانب البصرية

20. The brand reputation of the furniture influences my purchase decision.
 معة العلامة التجارية للأثاث تؤثر على قرار الشراء الخاص بي.
21. The color representation of products on the website is accurate.
 تمثيل ألوان المنتجات على الموقع دقيق.
22. The position of products on the website affects my likelihood of purchasing.
 موقع المنتجات على الموقع يؤثر على احتمالية شرائي.

F. Website Design / تصميم الموقع

23. The website's aesthetic design is appealing and professional.
 التصميم الجمالي للموقع جذاب ومهني.
24. The purchase process is straightforward and easy to follow.
 عملية الشراء واضحة و ههلة المتابعة.
25. The website is convenient to use and navigate.
 الموقع مريح للاستخدام والتصفح.
26. The website offers personalized recommendations based on my browsing history.
 يقدم الموقع توصيات مخصصة بناءً على تاريخ التصفح الخاص بي.
27. The website is always available and functions properly.
 الموقع متاح دائماً ويعمل بشكل صحيح.

G. Trust & Risk / الثقة والمخاطر

28. I trust this website with my personal and financial information.
 أثق في هذا الموقع بمعلوماتي الشخصية والمالية.
29. I am concerned about my privacy when shopping on this website.
 أقلق بشأن خصوصيتي عند التسوق على هذا الموقع.
30. I feel that my financial transactions on this website are secure.
 أشعر أن معاملاتي المالية على هذا الموقع آمنة.

H. Uncertainty / عدم اليقين

31. I am concerned about the risk of receiving a product that doesn't meet my expectations.
 أقلق بشأن خطر تلام منتج لا يلبي توقعاتي.
32. I worry about potential issues with delivery (delays, damages, etc.).
 أقلق بشأن المشاكل المحتملة مع التوصيل (التأخيرات، الأضرار، إلخ).
33. I am confident in the quality of products sold on this website.
 أواثق من جودة المنتجات المباعة على هذا الموقع.
34. I worry about how others might perceive my decision to buy furniture online.
 أقلق بشأن كيف قد ينظر الآخرون إلى قراري بشراء الأثاث عبر الإنترنت.

I. Payment Preferences / تفضيلات الدفع

35. I prefer to pay cash on delivery for my online furniture purchases.
 أفضل الدفع قداً عند التسليم لمشتريات الأثاث عبر الإنترنت.
36. I am comfortable using online payment methods for furniture purchases.
 أراحت ل استخدام طرق الدفع عبر الإنترنت لشراء الأثاث.
37. I would be more likely to purchase if multiple payment options were available at delivery.
 أكون أكثر احتمالاً للشراء إذا كانت هنا خيارات دفع متعددة متاحة عند التسليم.

J. Open-ended Questions / أسئلة مفتوحة

38. What is the main reason you would choose to buy furniture online instead of from a physical store?

ما هو السبب الرئيسي الذي يجعلك تختار شراء الأثاث عبر الإنترنت بدلاً من المتجر الفعلي؟

39. What improvements would you suggest for Homzmart.com to enhance your online furniture shopping experience?

ما هي التحسينات التي تقترحها لموقع Homzmart.com لتعزيز تجربة التسوق للأثاث عبر الإنترنت؟

40. Do you have any concerns about buying furniture online that haven't been addressed in this survey? If so, please explain.

هل لديك أي مخاوف بشأن شراء الأثاث عبر الإنترنت لم يتم تناولها في هذا الاستبيان؟ إذا كان الأمر كذلك، يرجى التوضيح.

Thank you for completing this survey. Your feedback is valuable and will help improve online furniture shopping experiences in Egypt.

شكراً لك على إكمال هذا الاستبيان. ملاحظتك قيمة وستساعد في تحسين تجارب التسوق للأثاث عبر الإنترنت في مصر.